

Contents

Acknowledgements	2
Organising committee	2
Sponsors & Exhibitors	3-5
General information	6-7
Programme at a glance	8-9
Invited speakers	10-12
Scientific Programme	13-21
Paper Abstracts	22-50
Poster Abstracts	51-57
SAHGCA sponsored session	58-60
Participant Contact List	61-69
About SAWMA	70

Hosted by:

The Department of
Economic Development,
Environment and
Tourism Limpopo Province
(LEDET)

Southern African Wildlife Management Association

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Acknowledgements

The Southern African Wildlife Management Association would like to thank the following people and organisations for their valuable contributions to SAWMA 2016:

- Host Organisation: The Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism Limpopo Province (LEDET)
- The organising and scientific committee
- Staff of the Tzaneen Country Lodge
- The adjudicators for student presentations
- The chair persons of the various sessions
- The Student Quiz convenors
- The symposium sponsors – see page 3-5
- The invited guest speakers – see page 10-12

Organising & Scientific Committee

Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism, Limpopo: Annemie De Klerk (co-ordinator) & Karen Steenkamp (Chair – Scientific committee), Johan Kruger, Vincent Egan & Errol Moeng. **SAWMA Council members:** Michael Somers (University of Pretoria), Craig Tambling (University of Fort Hare), Paul Grobler (University of the Free State) and Elma Marais (SAWMA secretariat).

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Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism, Limpopo

Sponsored session - "Bridging the divide" - The "currency" of the wildlife economy?

SA Hunters and Game Conservation Association (SAHGCA)

Student outing

SA Council for Natural Scientific Professions (SACNASP)

Wine

Partially sponsored by Antonij Rupert Wines: Protea brand

Printing of Programme Book

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Prizes

Cash prize (deserving project/paper which most effectively addresses challenges in the industry): SA Hunters and Game Conservation Association

Book prizes

- Jacana Publishers
- Bryan Pearce
- Gus Mills

Student Quiz:

Veeplaas

Student registration fees (partially):

SAWMA

Field trip (partially): LEDET

Exhibitors

Bryan Peirce (Adventures With Nature), SACNASP, Living in Harmony art display – Lajuma Research Centre

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General information

Important contact numbers during the symposium:

Elma Marais (SAWMA Secretariat) 071 352 3226

Cecilia Saunders (Tzaneen Country Lodge) 071 463 4129

Registration

The registration will be in the ALBIZIA HALL of the Tzaneen Convention Centre across the road from the Tzaneen Country Lodge. Registrations will be accepted during the following times: Sunday 18 September (16:00 – 18:00), Monday 19 September (07:30 – 08:00), Tuesday 20 September (07:30 – 08:00), and Wednesday 21 September (07:30 – 08:00). SAWMA does not have card facilities. Payments should be by EFT, cash or cheques.

Downloading of Presentations during registration

Papers & Posters – To ensure smooth running of the programme, we kindly request all presenters to submit their PowerPoint presentations during the **main registration on Sunday, 18 September** to the technical assistant for downloading documents onto the symposium laptop. If you intend to leave your memory stick with the technical assistant, please ensure that it is clearly marked and that the presentation document is saved using the title of the presentation. If not possible to submit it during the main registration presentations may also be submitted on the **day prior to presentation** during registration or tea times.

Affixing of Posters:

Poster presenters are requested to affix their posters at the designated exhibitor's area on Sunday 18 September during registration. Posters will be affixed to the wall and should be organised according to the numbers on the poster list in the programme. It is the responsibility of the presenters to remove their posters before 14:00 on Wednesday 21 September.

Student Quiz

For the first time the SAWMA Symposium will include a Student Quiz that will give students from the various academic institutions involved in conservation-related research, the opportunity to “showcase” their knowledge on the various fields that form part of conservation. The quiz will take place on Sunday, 18 September at 20:00 in Cassia Hall. Members of the audience may also participate. Only teams that entered by 12 September may take part.

Student Evaluations

Students will be eligible for book prizes for the best presentations.

When preparing your presentations (paper or poster), pay attention to the following criteria which will be used for the evaluation:

Evaluation criteria:

- (1) Scientific conceptual basis in the context of the conference theme (relevance, significance/impact of the work).
- (2) Approach of the investigation be it descriptive, experimental, comparative, meta-analytical or a review (quality of the research or methodology; logical sequence, e.g. (i) introduction including the research or management questions/objectives, (ii) some background information if applicable, (iii) results or management challenges, and (iv) conclusions and/or recommendations).
- (3) Oral delivery (clarity and audibility of the presentation, visual contact, use of time).
- (4) The use of visual aids (slide quality: clarity of slides, quality of images and figures; amount and size of text per slide; etc.).
- (5) Response to questions (clarity of explanations).

Meals

Breakfasts are part of the accommodation package and will be served at the respective venues where delegates are staying. All morning and afternoon teas, lunches and dinners during the symposium are covered by the full registration fees. Delegates registering on a daily basis may attend dinners at an additional cost. Lunches, Dinners including the Meet and Greet will be served on the deck areas of the Amphitheatre area of the convention Centre, depending on the weather conditions. The Gala dinner on 21 September will take place in the CASSIA HALL.

Cash Bar and Wine

Wines from Antonij Rupert (Protea Series) will be served during dinners, free of charge. A cash bar will also be available every evening for any other beverages.

Transport

Transport arrangements between the Tzaneen Country Lodge and Hotel@Tzaneen will be available on request. Contact Cecilia Saunders at 071 463 4129.

Wi-Fi

Free Wi-Fi is available in the rooms and the convention centre.

Post Symposium Field Trip

The post conference field trip on Thursday, 22 September will be to Modjadji Cycad Reserve (Modjadji Camp). The Modjadji Cycad Reserve is home to the biggest concentration of the rare endemic cycad, *Encephalartos transvenosus*, in the world. It will be a half day visit and lunch-packs will be included. Only pre-booked delegates can be included.

Programme at a Glance

Sunday, 18 September 2016

- 16:00 **Registration: ALBIZA HALL** [*Presenters to load presentations*]
18:00 **Meet and Greet: Amphitheatre deck at the Convention Centre**
Welcome: Dr Annemie de Klerk
20:00 **Student Quiz: CASSIA HALL**

Monday, 19 September 2016

- 07:30 Registration continues at ALBIZA HALL [*Presenters to load presentations*]
MAIN PRESENTATIONS IN THE CASSIA HALL
08:00 Presidential Welcome: Dr Harriet Davies-Mostert
08:10 Opening address: Mr Seaparo Sekoati - MEC for the Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism
08:30 Keynote speaker: Prof J du P (Koos) Bothma
09:00 **THEME: Growing the Wildlife Economy to create sustainable livelihoods**
10:15 **Tea: ALBIZA HALL**
10:45 **THEME: Wildlife Management Areas – balancing development pressure**
12:45 **Lunch: RESTAURANT / AMPHITHEATRE**
13:45 Poster Presentation Session and Questions
14:20 **THEME: Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (Herbivores)**
15:20 **Tea and Poster viewing: ALBIZA HALL**
15:45 **THEME: Principles and ethics in wildlife management – a paradigm shift**
17:00 SACNASP information session – Sarah van Aardt
17:15 **Game Salami Tasting Survey (voluntary!) – Monlee Swanepoel**
19:00 **Dinner: Amphitheatre deck at the Convention Centre**

Tuesday, 20 September 2016

- 07:30 Registration continues [*Presenters to load presentations*]
MAIN PRESENTATIONS IN THE CASSIA HALL
08:00 Keynote speaker: Prof Norman Owen-Smith
08:30 **THEME: Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (General)**
10:15 **Tea: ALBIZA HALL**
10:45 **THEME: Adapting Wildlife Management in the light of global change**
12:45 **Lunch: RESTAURANT / AMPHITHEATRE**

- 13:45 Poster Presentation Session
- 14:40 **Tea and poster viewing: ALBIZA HALL**
- 15:30 SAWMA Annual General Meeting & election of a council for 2016-2018
- 16:30 Student pre-dinner outing to a local pub: Maxims
- 19:00 **Dinner: Amphitheatre deck at the Convention Centre**
- 20:30 **Documentary: To Skin a Cat**

Wednesday, 21 September 2016

- 07:30 Registration continues [*Presenters to load presentations*]
- MAIN PRESENTATIONS IN THE CASSIA HALL**
- 08:00 Keynote speaker: Dr MGL (Gus) Mills
- 08:30 **THEME: Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (big cats)**
- 10:00 **Tea: ALBIZA HALL**
- 10:30 **THEME: Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (carnivores & other)**
- 12:00 **Lunch: RESTAURANT / AMPHITHEATRE**
- 13:00 **THEME: Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (carnivores & other)**
- 14:15 **Tea: ALBIZA HALL**
- 14:40 **SAHGCA Sponsored Session: "Bridging the divide" - The "currency" of the wildlife economy?**
- 18:30 Gala Dinner, prize giving, and closure: CASSIA HALL**

Thursday, 22 September 2016

- 08:00 Optional field trip to Modjadji Cycad Reserve. (Pre-booked only!)

Invited Speakers

Emeritus Professor J du P (Koos) Bothma

Keynote address – Monday, 19 September: The evolution of commercial wildlife production in South Africa

Jacobus du Plessis Bothma matriculated at the Helpmekaar Boys High School in Johannesburg in 1957 and did his military service at the South African Air Force Gymnasium in 1958. He received a Bachelor's degree in Botany and Zoology at the University of Pretoria in 1962, followed by a Master's degree in Zoology at the University of Pretoria in 1964.

He was appointed as a Professional Officer in the former Division of Nature Conservation of the Transvaal Province in 1964, and was granted salaried leave in 1965 to obtain a PhD degree in Wildlife and Fisheries Science at Texas A&M University, Texas, USA where he graduated in 1969 and returned to his post.

He was seconded permanently to the new Eugène Marais Chair of Wildlife Management at the Department of Zoology of the University of Pretoria on 1 January 1970, with the rank of Senior Lecturer, was promoted to Associate Professor in 1971 and to Full Professor in 1981.

He became the Director of the new post-graduate Centre for Wildlife Management in the Department of Animal and Wildlife Sciences at the University of Pretoria in 1989 until he retired in 2005. In his academic career he trained 380 BSc (Honours), 52 MSc and 11 PhD graduates in wildlife management.

Among others he was a Founder Member of the Southern African Wildlife Management Association and President in 1975, the President of the South African Biological Society in 1980 and the Chairman of the Board of Directors, Tourism and Nature Conservation Corporation of Qwaqwa. He was a Member of the Board of Trustees for the Transvaal Museum, a Co-founder of The Endangered Wildlife Trust of South Africa and a Member of its Scientific Advisory Board, a Member of the Advisory Board of the Mammal Research Institute of the University of Pretoria and a Founder Member of the Southern African Institute of Ecologists and Environmental Scientists. He also was the President of the University of Pretoria Rugby Club.

He received the Award as the Best Senior Student in Biology at Helpmekaar Boys High School, was a Welder Wildlife Foundation Fellow in Texas, USA, received the Senior Captain Scott Memorial Medal for exemplary biological research from the South African Academy of Science and Art, received the Order of the Bataleur for his contributions to wildlife production and conservation from the South African Hunters and Wildlife Conservation Association,

received the prestigious Tuks Alumni Award of Excellence from the University of Pretoria, was Listed as a Notable Alumnus of the University of Pretoria and was nominated for the Bill Venter Literary Award for his Game Ranch Management books. He was rated as a researcher by the National Research Foundation.

To date he has been the editor, author, co-author or contributor to 21 books, the author or co-author of 102 refereed scientific papers, and the author of 246 popular science papers. He has presented 37 papers on national and 29 papers on international conferences. He is still active as a national and international wildlife consultant and writer.

Emeritus Professor Norman Owen-Smith

Keynote address – Tuesday, 20 September: Large herbivore management and the concept of carrying capacity.

Norman Owen-Smith received his MSc degree from the University of Natal in 1965 and PhD from the University of Wisconsin in 1973 for a study on the behavioural ecology of the white rhinoceros. Following a postdoctoral fellowship at the University of Pretoria, he took up a lectureship at the University of Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe) for the Masters programme in Tropical Resource Ecology.

He joined Wits University in 1979 as Research Officer first in Applied Mathematics, then in Botany. In 1987 he was appointed Senior Lecturer in the Department of Zoology, being promoted to Reader in 1991 and Research Professor in African Ecology in 1997, the position he held until his retirement at the end of 2007.

His research field encompasses the ecology of large mammalian herbivores, their interactions with vegetation, and savanna ecology more generally. He has supervised studies in Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia and Mozambique as well as in South Africa. In 1999 he was awarded an A-rating by the National Research Foundation in recognition of his scientific status. He is a Fellow of the Royal Society of South Africa, Honorary Life Member of the Ecological Society of America. He received Gold Medal Awards from the Zoological Society of South Africa and the Southern African Association for the Advancement of Science, and the Bill Venter/Altron Literary Award for his book "Adaptive Herbivore Ecology". He has written or edited five books and has had over 145 articles published in scientific journals or as book chapters.

Currently he is Research Professor Emeritus in the School of Animal, Plant and Environmental Sciences at the University of the Witwatersrand, and still actively engaged in research.

Dr Michael (Gus) Mills

Keynote address - Wednesday, 21 September: History and future of large carnivore conservation research and management in South Africa

Gus Mills spent 40 years conducting research on African large carnivores with SANParks in the Kgalagadi Transfrontier and Kruger National Parks. His initial work was on brown hyaenas and spotted hyaenas in the Southern Kalahari, culminating in the publication of his book in 1990 "Kalahari hyaenas: the comparative behavioural ecology of two species." He studied lion and cheetah feeding ecology, ecological relationships between the large carnivores, and wild dog population ecology in Kruger National Park, before returning to the Kalahari in 2006 to undertake a six-year study on the cheetah, under the auspices of the Lewis Foundation, the results of which will be published in a book due to be released in October 2016.

He has supervised a number of PhD and MSc theses on aspects of lion, cheetah, wild dog, brown hyaena, honey badger and African wild cat behaviour and ecology in different areas of Southern Africa. He was the founder of the Endangered Wildlife Trust's Carnivore Conservation Group.

He has written five books and authored or co-authored over 150 scientific papers, as well as delivered over 80 talks at conferences and symposia worldwide. He is a senior member of several IUCN Carnivore Specialist Groups, including former Chair of the Hyaena Specialist Group, and member of the steering committees of the Cat Specialist Group and the Canid Specialist Group. He has served as a member on several boards of conservation organizations and scientific journals, including African Journal of Wildlife Research, and consulted widely on carnivore conservation issues in Africa and Asia.

Scientific Programme:

Sustainable Wildlife Management: Striking a balance?

Sunday 18 September 2016

16:00 **Registration: ALBIZA HALL**

18:00 **Meet and Greet: Amphitheatre Deck of the Convention Centre**

Welcome: Dr Annemie de Klerk – Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism, Limpopo Province (Host of SAWMA 2016)

20:00 **Student Quiz: CASSIA HALL**

Monday 19 September 2016

07:30 Registration continues

PRESENTATIONS IN CASSIA HALL

Chair: Paul Grobler (University of the Free State)

08:00 Welcome: Dr Harriet T Davies-Mostert (SAWMA President)

08:10 Opening address: Mr Seaparo Sekoati - MEC for the Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism

08:30 **Invited Keynote Presentation: The evolution of commercial wildlife production in South Africa. Prof J du P (Koos) Bothma**

Growing the Wildlife Economy to create sustainable livelihoods

09:00 Wildlife economy and sustainability: is there a link? Sibongiseni Hlabisa

09:15 Illegal bushmeat hunters compete with predators, threatening herbivore populations in a global tourism hotspot. Matthew S Rogan, Peter A Lindsey, Craig J Tambling, Krystyn A Golabeka, Michael J Chase, Kai Collins & J Weldon McNutt

09:30 Game meat production on private land: current scale and potential for the future. Andrew Taylor, Matthew Child, Peter A Lindsey & Harriet T Davies-Mostert

09:45 Game Ranching and Biodiversity Conservation: Encouraging a mutually beneficial partnership. SA Jeanetta Selier & Andrew Taylor

10:00 Evaluation of Baga Bareki Farm as part of wildlife transformation within the Northern Cape Province, South Africa. Christina F Kraft & Marnus Z Smit

10:15 **Tea**

Chair: Frans Radloff (Cape Peninsula University of Technology)

**Wildlife Management Areas –
balancing development pressure**

10:45 Leopard movement dynamics and densities shaped by various human induced influences. Gerrie Camacho

11:00 Low-level fences reduce roadkill at hotspots: a South African example. Wendy J Collinson, Warwick Davies-Mostert, Harriet T Davies-Mostert

11:15 Spatio-temporal analysis of dog distribution and rabies epidemiology at a wildlife interface in the Lowveld region of South Africa. Michael R Grover, Darryn Knobel, Anne Conan & Paul Bessel

11:30 The role of access to justice in enabling sustainable wildlife use in the Southern African Development Community Transfrontier Conservation Areas. Louise S Kavinga

11:45 Qualifying the effect/impact of artificial water points on the Madikwe landscape. H Pieter Nel & Mpho Sekgarametso

12:00 Twenty years of wildlife-powerline interaction monitoring and mitigating: balancing conservation and corporate costs. Samantha Page-Nicholson & Constant Hoogstad

12:15 Sustainable management of wildlife pests: The gerbil problem in balance? Emil von Maltitz, Frikkie Kirsten, Lourens Swanepoel & Mark Keith

12:30 Managing the relationship between mining and wildlife destinations - with specific reference to World Heritage Sites. Annemie de Klerk

12:45 **Lunch**

Poster Presentation Session

Chair: David Marneweck (The Endangered Wildlife Trust)

13:45 1) Eskom/Endangered Wildlife Trust partnership 1996 – 2016: 20 years of working together to reduce impacts of the business on biodiversity and vice versa. Constant Hoogstad, Kishaylin Chetty & Megan Murison

13:50 2) Seeking roadkill data through public awareness, partnerships and citizen science. Wendy J Collinson, Claire Patterson-Abrolat, Samantha Page-Nicholson, Thandiwe Rakale, Miles le Roux, Charmaine van Wyk & Lizanne Roxburgh

- 13:55 3) Adaptive genetic variation within southern African mammal species. Willem G Coetzer, Rudi Lombaard, Sakhumzi Ngoma & J Paul Grobler
- 14:00 4) *Ongediertes*: A critical qualitative study of the political ecology of black-backed jackal and its management around the SKA core site. Renelle Terblanche
- 14:05 5) The dietary consequences of being an urban caracal: insight from classic and new methods. Gabriella Leighton, Jacqueline Bishop, Joleen Broadfield, Justin Johnson, Justin O’Riain and & Laurel Serieys
- 14:10 **Poster question/discussion session (10 mins)**

Chair: Errol Moeng (Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism, Limpopo)

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (Herbivores)

- 14:20 Spatial ecology and habitat use of GPS fitted giraffe in the Kalahari region of South Africa. Francois Deacon & G Nico Smit
- 14:35 Vegetation density reflects small ungulate refuge habitat from predation. Craig J Tambling, Andrew B Davies, Liaan Minnie, Gregory P Asner & Graham IH Kerley
- 14:50 Framing the Riverine Rabbit (*Bunolagus monticularis*); modelling camera trap data from the Klein Karoo. Zoë A Woodgate, M Justin O’Riain, Greg Distiller & Christy Bragg
- 15:05 A viable tool for hybrid detection in wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus* and *C. gnou*). J Paul Grobler, Anri Van Wyk, Desire Dalton & Antoinette Kotze

15:20 **Tea and poster viewing in ALBIZA HALL**

Chair: Kelly Marnewick (The Endangered Wildlife Trust)

Principles and ethics in wildlife management – a paradigm shift

- 15:45 Anti-furtive inspection techniques in conservation areas: case study of Chimanimani National Reserve (RNC). Zefanias J Magodo
- 16:00 The use of permanent passageways in fences to accommodate warthog movement. Monlee Swanepoel, Alison J Leslie & Louwrens C Hoffman
- 16:15 Under what circumstances can wildlife farming benefit species conservation? Laura Tensen

- 16:30 Baboon management success? Can a shift in paradigm assist future management of baboons? Jenni Trethowan
- 16:45 Remotely operated virtual fences: a successful new approach to baboon management. Philip RK Richardson, Everhard C Conradie, Phillip A Olivier, Sieglinde C Rode, Byron Loubser, Catherine Shutte, Robyn E Khoury & Hayley M Wittridge
- 17:00 SACNASP INFORMATION SESSION – Sarah van Aardt
- 17:15 Salami Tasting Survey: Monlee Swanepoel
- 19:00 Dinner**

Tuesday 20 September 2016

- 07:30 Registration continues

Chair: Pieter Nel (North West Parks Board)

- 08:00 **Invited Keynote Presentation: Large herbivore management and the concept of carrying capacity. Prof Norman Owen-Smith**

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (General)

- 08:30 The state of our mammals: how far have we come and where are we going? Matthew Child, Lizanne Roxburgh, Domitilla Raimond, Andrew Taylor & Harriet T Davies-Mostert
- 08:45 Unravelling a Kalahari Desert food chain using stable isotopes, can it teach us anything new? Frans GT Radloff, Alexander Bond, Maya Beukes & Otto Beukes
- 09:00 The impact of DDT on the bone X-ray density and bone length of the House Sparrow in designated areas of the Limpopo Province. Lindi Steyn, Hindrik Bouwman & John N Maina
- 09:15 The farmer's friend: The success story of Wakkerstroom's Secretarybirds. Eleen Strydom, Gerard Malan, Hanneline Smit-Robinson & Ernst Retief
- 09:30 Guidelines for habitat management: The influence of slope on population expansion of *Euphorbia clivicola*. R.A. Dyer. A Case Study. Seloba I Chuene, Johan W Kruger & Martin J Potgieter
- 09:45 The diet selection of extralimital giraffe in Albany Thicket vegetation within the Little Karoo region of South Africa. Jamie Paulse, Vanessa Couldridge, Clement Cupido & Francois Deacon

10:00 The ecological impact of elephant herbivory on vegetation of Atherstone Collaborative Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Makoshane Q Seloana, Martin J Potgieter, Johan W Kruger & Jorrie J Jordaan

10:15 **Tea**

Chair: Louw Hoffman (University of Stellenbosch)

Adapting Wildlife Management in the light of global change

10:45 The managed metapopulation approach for Cheetah conservation: A suitable technique outside of South Africa? Vincent C van der Merwe & Kelly Marnewick

11:00 Environmental Leadership: Exploring environmental dissonance involving natural resource consumption and ecosystem degradation. Thomas L Tocherman

11:15 Fear factor: the effects of a varying predation pressure and vegetation structure on prey species in a novel wetland ecosystem. Kevin W Emslie, Lourens Swanepoel, Stefan Foord, Daan Look, Wayne Matthews

11:30 Stakeholder perceptions towards climate change impacts on wildlife resources: implications for wildlife management in the Middle Zambezi Biosphere Reserve, Zimbabwe. Olga L Kupika & Edson Gandiwa

11:45 The evolution of wild dog (*Lycaon pictus*) metapopulation management in South Africa. David G Marneweck, Kelly Marnewick, Brendan Whittington-Jones & Harriet T Davies-Mostert

12:00 Managing to save the rhino in the Limpopo Province? Karen Steenkamp & Riaan de Jager

12:15 The spatial and dietary ecology of baboons in conflict with sheep farmers in the Karoo. Marion Tafani, M Justin O'Riain, Marine Drouilly & Nicoli Nattrass

12:30 A scenario supposition of the effects on ecological systems by hydraulic fracturing in the Nama Karoo, South Africa. Jan Arkert

12:45 **Lunch**

Poster Presentation Session

Chair: Maartin Strauss (University of South Africa)

13:45 6) Deriving a practical biodiversity value score for Protected Areas in Limpopo. Vincent T Egan

13:50 7) Big trees versus big elephants: Is there room for both? Henry M van Lelyveld & Yolanda Pretorius

- 13:55 8) Using DNA from Giraffe (*Giraffa camelopardalis*) faecal samples to determine diversity within populations. Marika E van Niekerk, Francois Deacon, J Paul Grobler
- 14:00 9) Mammal diversity and density in transformed and natural landscapes of a conservation corridor adjacent to the Garden Route National Park, Western Cape Province. Samantha Schimmel & Jan A Venter
- 14:05 **Poster question/discussion session (10 mins)**
- 14:15 10) Impala spatial and temporal habitat utilization and movement patterns. Precilla Stiglingh, Leslie R Brown & Alan S Barrett
- 14:20 11) Using non-invasive genetic sampling to assess population size and genetic viability of isolated black rhino populations. Nikki le Roex, Michael Paxton, John Adendorff, Markus Hofmeyr, Dave Zimmerman, Angela Gaylard & M Justin O’Riain
- 14:25 12) Carnivore intra-guild competition at Selati Game Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. Jessica Comley & Dan M Parker
- 14:30 13) Amphibians and vegetation as indicators of conservation value of wetlands in an anthropogenically impacted landscape. Emily Jones, Tineke Kraaij & Jan A Venter
- 14:35 14) Herpetological biodiversity in areas adjacent to the Wilderness Section of the Garden Route National Park, Western Cape, South Africa. Petro Rossouw & Jan A Venter
- 14:40 **Poster question/discussion session (10 mins)**
- 14:50 **Tea and poster viewing in ALBIZA HALL**
- 15:30 **ANNUAL GENERAL MEETING AND COUNCIL ELECTION: SAWMA**
- 16:30 Student pre-dinner outing to Maxims
- 19:00 **Dinner**
- 20:30 **Documentary: “To Skin a Cat” – CASSIA HALL**

Wednesday 21 September 2016

07:30 Registration continues

Chair: Dan Parker (University of Mpumalanga)

08:00 **Invited Keynote Presentation: History and future of large carnivore conservation research and management in South Africa. Dr MGL (Gus) Mills**

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (big cats)

08:30 Spotting changes? A national leopard monitoring plan for South Africa. Gareth KH Mann, Ross Pitman & Guy A Balme

08:45 Population density trends and threats to leopards outside protected areas. Samual T Williams, Kathryn S Williams & Russell A Hill

09:00 The cat is out of the bag: a preliminary review of the scale of the illegal leopard skin trade in southern Africa. Vincent Naude, Gareth M Whittington-Jones, Tristan Dickerson & Guy A Balme

09:15 The dilemma of lions (*Panthera leo*) in small reserves and consequences for management. Orla K McEvoy, Sam M Ferreira & Dan M Parker

09:30 Aging traits and sustainable trophy hunting of African lions. Jennie RB Miller, Paul J Funston, Peter Lindsey & Guy A Balme

09:45 Age and sex identification from digital 3D models of lion paws using geometric morphometrics. Antoine FJ Marchal, P Lejeune, & PJ Nico de Bruyn

10:00 Tea

Chair: Michael Somers (University of Pretoria)

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (carnivores & other)

10:30 Trends in Crocodile populations in the Olifants and Letaba Rivers, Limpopo Province, outside the Kruger National Park. Vincent T Egan, S Stanley & M Rodgers

10:45 Habitat use and predator influence on honey badgers in iSimangaliso Wetland Park, South Africa. Enhle ZY Kheswa, Tharmalingam Ramesh, Riddhika Kalle & Colleen T Downs

- 11:00 Logistic population growth and vital rates of African wild dogs (*Lycaon pictus*) in Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park, KZN: patterns and implications. David G Marneweck, Dave J Druce, Kelly Marnewick & Michael J Somers
- 11:15 Spotted hyena (*Crocuta crocuta*) habitat use across a land use gradient in western Zimbabwe. Mlamuleli Mhlanga, Hillary T Madiri, Tharmalingam Ramesh, Riddhika Kalle & Colleen T Downs
- 11:30 Impacts of urbanization on the distribution, diet and health of the Cape clawless otter, *Aonyx capensis*, in the Western Cape, South Africa. Nicola C Okes, M Justin O’Riain
- 11:45 Using technology-based data collection and wildlife crime analysis to combat poaching: a case study at Balule Nature Reserve. Andrew Taylor, Pieter Botha, Adam Pires, Craig Spencer, Lisa Trueman & Andrew M Lemieux
- 12:00 **Lunch**
- Chair: Craig Tambling (University of Fort Hare)**
- Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (carnivores & other)**
- 13:00 Prevalence and diversity of tick-borne pathogens in caracals and jackals in human-modified landscapes. Storme Viljoen, M Justin O’Riain, Banie L Penzhorn, Marine Drouilly, Bogdan Cristescu, Kristine J Teichman, Laurel EK Serieys & Jacqueline M Bishop
- 13:15 Assessing diet, prey preference and niche overlap of sympatric mesocarnivores on farmland versus a nature reserve. Marine Drouilly, Nicoli Natrass, Beatrice Conradie & M Justin O’Riain
- 13:30 Urbanization drives genetic divergence in the isolated Cape Peninsula caracal (*Caracal caracal*) population. Laurel EK Serieys, Shaelynn Squires, Robert K Wayne, Marine Drouilly, Kristine Teichman, Bogdan Cristecu, M Justin O’Riain & Jacqueline Bishop
- 13:45 Evaluating sustainable international trade in wildlife using Non-detriment Finding Assessments: barriers and opportunities. Kelly Marnewick & SA Jeanetta Selier
- 14:00 Hit and run! Reducing wildlife-vehicle-collisions in protected areas. Wendy J Collinson, Lizanne Roxburgh, Harriet.T Davies-Mostert
- 14:15 **Tea**

AMPHITHEATRE DECK OF THE CONVENTION CENTRE

**SAHGCA Sponsored Session: “Bridging the divide” –
The “currency” of the wildlife economy?**

Chair: Harriet Davies-Mostert (The Endangered Wildlife Trust)

- 14:40 Introduction: Lizanne Nel
- 14:45 National Parks for Society – Rationale, challenges and opportunities. Louise K Swemmer, Daniel J Pienaar & Helen A Mmethi
- 15:00 The Currency of Farmed Wildlife in southern Africa: a master quest of environmental health, bio-economic growth and species enhancement. Deon Furstenburg
- 15:15 The conservation costs of game ranching. Ross Tyzack Pitman, Julien Fattebert, Samuel T Williams, Kathryn S Williams, Russell A Hill, Luke TB Hunter, Rob Slotow & Guy A Balme (Johan Kruger will present the paper on behalf of Ross Pitman)
- 15:30 The environmental costs of intensive game breeding in South Africa: Mapping the rate of change in game fences at two sites in Limpopo Province from 2006-2015. Phillip Desmet & Lizanne EJ Nel
- 15:45 Desperation to Opportunity: Protected areas unlocking rural wildlife economies? Andrew Blackmore & Lizanne EJ Nel
- 16:00 Biodiversity economy nodes – fostering simultaneous achievement of conservation and economic targets. Lizanne EJ Nel
- 16:00 -16:30 **Questions and debate**

Master of Ceremony: Annemie de Klerk

19:00 Gala Dinner, prize and medals, closure

Paper Abstracts

Monday, 19 September 2016

**Invited Keynote address:
The evolution of commercial wildlife production in South Africa**

J du P Bothma

Former Director, Centre for Wildlife Management, University of Pretoria, South Africa

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Private ownership of and the commercial production of wildlife in South Africa became possible with the promulgation of Game Theft Act 105 of 1991, as amended in 1996 and 2000. Since then the commercial production of wildlife in South Africa has gone through various phases.

The first phase involved the removal of livestock from marginal livestock production units and restocking them mainly with indigenous plains wildlife to create the first wildlife ranches. The second phase was the additional production of rarer indigenous wildlife. Both phases aimed at economic gains based on conservation principles through extensive wildlife production, with ecotourism, live sales, recreational and trophy hunting of wildlife as the main forms of sustainable use. However, the live wildlife auctions function on the economic laws of supply and demand and have the potential for large financial gains but also of considerable losses. Recently, the production of exotic wildlife, colour and morphological variants has been added purely for financial gain.

Few, if any, other countries have such a large wildlife resource under the protection of private landowners. Yet the genetic consequences of the production of fragmented wildlife populations in isolation through effective wildlife fencing without proper genetic management and their impact on the conservation of the biodiversity of South Africa are still largely unknown.

The evolution, conservation threats and benefits of the commercial production of wildlife in South Africa and some recommendations are discussed briefly.

Growing the Wildlife Economy to create sustainable livelihoods

Wildlife economy and sustainability: is there a link?

Sibongiseni B Hlabisa

Nature Conservation, Department of Environmental Sciences, University of South Africa, South Africa

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The assumption that wildlife economic activities are, by their very nature, sustainable is widely accepted and is rarely placed under scrutiny. For instance, it is argued that wildlife conservation and production areas avert the ecologically destructive land transformation processes associated with mainstream economic activities. This paper examines this presumed sustainability of wildlife conservation and production activities from a supply-side perspective and under three themes. The first theme concerns the connections between wildlife economic activities and the mainstream economy. The second theme is concerned with the sustainability of inputs (energetic and material) into wildlife management. The last theme is concerned with the institutional sustainability of wildlife management. The results that emerged from a systematic review of the literature demonstrate that the wildlife economy is an extension of and is embedded within the mainstream economic processes that it seeks to mitigate. That is, it is dependent on inputs derived from and generated by the more

intensive land-use types. There has also been an ever increasing institutional complexity and costs associated with wildlife management. Thus, the sustainability of the wildlife economy cannot be simply supposed. It is a goal towards which wildlife managers must strive in much the same way as all the other economic activities.

Illegal bushmeat hunters compete with predators, threatening herbivore populations in a global tourism hotspot

**Matthew S Rogan^{1,2,3}, Peter A Lindsey^{2,4}, Craig J Tambling⁵, Krystyna A Golabek¹,
Michael J Chase⁶, Kai Collins^{4,7} & J Weldon McNutt¹**

¹ Botswana Predator Conservation Trust, Maun, Botswana

² Panthera, New York, United States of America

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⁴ Mammal Research Institute, Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of Pretoria Pretoria, South Africa

⁵ Centre for African Conservation Ecology, Department of Zoology, Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University, Port Elizabeth, South Africa

⁶ Elephants Without Borders, Kasane, Botswana

⁷ Wilderness Safaris, Maun, Botswana

Presenter: Matthew Rogan, Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Private Bag X3, Rondebosch 7701, Cape Town, +27 (0)76 709 3076, mrogan@panthera.org

Illegal bushmeat hunting is a widespread threat to wildlife globally, but its secretive and unregulated nature undermines efforts to mitigate its impacts on wildlife and wildlife-based industries. We investigated the scale of illegal bushmeat hunting and its potential contribution to declining wildlife populations in a network of Wildlife Management Areas in the Okavango Delta, Botswana (~20,000 km²). Based on interviews with hunters and heads of village households, we estimate the total number of illegal bushmeat hunters living around the delta, and the total number of animals killed and mass of meat harvested annually. Approximately 576-1,902 (best estimate = 1,775) illegal hunters each harvest an average of 163-235 kg of bushmeat (dressed weight) annually, though some reported harvesting ≥1,000 kg. We estimate that hunters remove approximately 650,000 kg of herbivore biomass (equivalent to 16,250 impala) annually from the delta. Hunters' and predators' cumulative consumption likely exceeds the intrinsic population growth rate of several species of medium and large herbivores in the periphery of the delta, and may result in sink effects within protected areas that reduce the resilience of wildlife populations to the natural ecological fluctuations that characterize the delta ecosystem. Competition between humans and other apex predators for limited prey reduces the ecosystem's carrying capacity for large carnivores. To address the negative impacts of illegal bushmeat hunting in northern Botswana, better strategies are required to ensure that members of local communities derive direct benefits from wildlife resources, while simultaneously curbing illegal hunting through effective law enforcement.

Game meat production on private land: current scale and potential for the future

Andrew Taylor¹, Matthew Child^{1,2}, Peter A Lindsey³ & Harriet T Davies-Mostert^{1,2}

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² Centre for Wildlife Management, University of Pretoria, South Africa

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Game meat production is considered one of the four pillars of wildlife ranching in South Africa, with the potential to generate large revenues and contribute positively to food security and job creation. It is very far from meeting its potential, however, with the main reason for this being a lack of an enabling

legislation to allow for large scale game meat production.

This situation is changing, and as the opportunities for game meat production open up, the wildlife ranching industry is planning the way forward. Based on background information on the sector from available literature, interviews with expert stakeholders, as well as data collected during a survey of 250 wildlife ranchers across South Africa, we examine the current and potential scales of the sector and assess the potential future contribution game meat production could make to food security and job creation. Although there are no accurate estimates of current domestic game meat production for South Africa, anecdotal estimates suggest that 10-20% of meat consumed during the hunting season is game meat, which equates to 45 000-118 000 tonnes. By comparison, our study estimated ~40 000 tonnes of game meat were produced during 2014. With the possibility of a new game meat scheme, domestic production could be increased considerably. Producing sustainable sources of protein in social-ecological systems is also touted as a key intervention to possibly reduce bushmeat poaching and biodiversity loss. Generating game meat sustainably may thus be win-win for ecologists and the economy.

Game Ranching and Biodiversity Conservation: Encouraging a mutually beneficial partnership

SA Jeanetta Selier¹ & Andrew Taylor²

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South Africa's terrestrial protected area network falls far short of the 12% agreed to by the country for AICHI biodiversity target 11. Further legislation will not assist in the procurement of additional land under biodiversity protection. In order for government to meet this target the assistance of the private sector is required. At present private wildlife ranches and reserves measure approximately 20 500 000 hectares, 16% of the total hectares in South Africa. However, the current contribution of the private sector to biodiversity conservation is unknown. The industry thinks it is high, while in many cases regulators and conservation organisations believe the opposite. In addition the industry contribution to biodiversity conservation is not secure. Wildlife ranchers on the whole have different objectives to conservation managers with economics as the primary driver within the wildlife industry. For the industry thus to become involved in biodiversity conservation and specifically the protected areas network, a mutually beneficial partnership with economic incentives for partaking in biodiversity conservation and forming part of the protected areas network will need to be developed. In this paper we suggest the development of a green flagging system and discuss the mechanisms and challenges for incentivising good biodiversity management practice in the wildlife industry.

Evaluation of Baga Bareki Farm as part of wildlife transformation within the Northern Cape Province, South Africa

Christina F Kraft & Marnus Z Smit

Department of Environment and Nature Conservation, Northern Cape Province, South Africa

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The Department of Environmental Affairs have initiated a number of wildlife transformation projects, following the Biodiversity Economy Strategy of South Africa, to stimulate economic growth for local community beneficiation. One such project includes the conversion of Baga Bareki farm within the Northern Cape Province into a viable commercial game ranch. A habitat assessment was conducted to determine the suitability of the farm for game ranching by determining the species composition, veld condition, carrying capacity and game species suitability.

A total of 13 transects (250 m² each) were demarcated within the four identified vegetation types. All the vegetation types were in a poor condition due to the dominance of undesirable annual plants. The average grazing capacity of 17.2 ha/Grazer Unit was almost half than that of the known long term grazing capacity of the region. The main causes for this were overgrazing and low rainfall. Browsing capacity varied from 3.4 to 17.4 ha/Browser Unit and was regarded as high for a semi-arid environment. This could be attributed to bush thickening which affected most of the vegetation types. The game species suitability model revealed that only some arid adapted game species could be suitable for introduction at low densities.

Apart from the ecological limitations, additional challenges identified which could affect the suitability of the farm included a lack of water resources, insufficient infrastructure, un-rehabilitated mining sites and poaching. It could be concluded that Baga Bareki farm was not suitable for game ranching and that alternative options for economic development should be investigated.

Wildlife Management Areas – balancing development pressure

Leopard Movement Dynamics and Densities shaped by various Human induced influences

Gerrie Camacho

Scientific Services, Terrestrial, Carnivora Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency, Mpumalanga, South Africa

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Three male leopards ageing two years and six years of age showed typical spatial dynamics although shaped by conditions created by human development and activities. Leopard densities and demographics in the Manyeleti Game Reserve could be shaped by other human induced factors such as hard boundaries, domestic animal behaviour and disease control. The impact of escalating illegal take-off and Human/Wildlife Conflict issues are all disturbing factors as they are mostly immeasurable and any risk assessment for future population trend predictions seems impossible. The Conservative Conservation Strategy approach seems the way forward but has numerous challenges.

Low-level fences reduce roadkill at hotspots: a South African example

Wendy J Collinson¹, Warwick Davies-Mostert² & Harriet T Davies-Mostert^{1,3}

¹*The Endangered Wildlife Trust, South Africa*

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A wide variety of mitigation measures are deployed to reduce wildlife mortality on roads, but few of these have been tested in South Africa, where road ecology is still an emerging field. During baseline roadkill surveys conducted in 2009 in the Greater Mapungubwe Transfrontier Conservation Area (GMTFCA), a UNESCO World Heritage Site in Limpopo province South Africa, we identified the presence of a roadkill hotspot. Such hotspots are characterized by higher than average concentrations of roadkill and therefore provide an opportunity to initiate targeted mitigation measures with relatively high potential impact. In early 2015, we investigated the efficacy of roadside barriers in reducing mortality frequency of small terrestrial vertebrates in the hotspot. We erected low-level fencing by the roadside to direct wildlife towards existing culverts beneath the road, and compared mortality frequency before and after the intervention. We observed a sharp decrease in the concentration of roadkill events where the barriers were erected (from 0.23 roadkills/day/km to 0.04 roadkills/day/km), as compared to control sites, although this decline was not quite significant (Friedman's test, $\chi^2 = 0.1$, $p = 0.09$), probably due to the small sample size. Our results suggest that low-level fencing can reduce the incidence of roadkill for small terrestrial vertebrates, although its potential negative effects, for example on population connectivity, still need to be investigated.

Spatio-temporal analysis of dog distribution and rabies epidemiology at a wildlife interface in the Lowveld region of South Africa

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Presenter: Michael Grover, Djuma Game Reserve, Hluvukani 1363, +27 (0)83 575 5201, mike@activatingafrica.com

It's estimated that free-roaming domestic dogs (*Canis familiaris*) comprise 75% of dog populations (where?). Even with extensive fences dogs are still enter the reserves. The study reserve in the Lowveld of South Africa has a high density of human settlements on its boundary. These communities own dogs, many of which are free-roaming. Between January 2009 and March 2014, 170 stray dogs were destroyed inside the reserve and 65.3% of the samples returned a positive result for rabies. Dogs are not limited to the reserve edges and have been documented several kilometres within the reserve.

The distribution of the dogs shot was spatially analyzed to determine correlation to geographical influences. This was done using eleven geographical factors and the nearest distance to each factor was determined. Generalized linear models (GLM) were then used to analyse the distance data of dogs shot to the nearest factor. Dogs were significantly more likely to be shot further away from anti-poaching outposts and closer to minor rivers. To remove the effect of the fence an analysis of the subset of dogs found further than 200 m into the reserve found a positive association between distance from a village and a positive rabies test result ($p = 0.007$).

The spatial results gives management an indication to increase efforts to destroy domestic dogs further into the reserve as the likelihood of a positive rabies result is greater.

The role of access to justice in enabling sustainable wildlife use in the Southern African Development Community Transfrontier Conservation Areas

Louise S Kavinga

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The Southern African Development Community region has much wildlife which is socially and economically important. The establishment of Transfrontier Conservation Areas is an initiative which promotes economic growth, social development and sustainable use of natural resources within and across borders of different countries.

Wildlife conservation in a transfrontier setting could arguably be improved if there is stability and peaceful relations across borders. Therefore, the local communities in and around the Transfrontier Conservation Areas must have legal recourse, remedies and generally, access to justice when tension and conflict arise. However, unlike the Protocol to the Southern African Development Community Tribunal of 2000 which had comprehensive provisions on access to justice, the proposed Protocol to the Southern African Development Community Tribunal of 2014 narrows the scope of jurisdiction in the Tribunal. Individuals and private actors such as Non-Governmental Organisations are overlooked despite the important role they play in ensuring the success of wildlife conservation. The paper points out why restricted access to a supranational court will pose a threat to sustainable wildlife use and conservation in the Southern African Development Community Transfrontier Conservation Areas. This presentation is based on a desktop analysis of literature on the legal and policy framework of wildlife conservation in the Southern African Development Community region.

Qualifying the effect/impact of artificial water points on the Madikwe landscape

H Pieter Nel & Mpho Sekgarametso

Conservation Management Division, North West Parks Board, North West Province, South Africa

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Madikwe is located in a semi-arid savanna region on the north-western border of North West Province, South Africa. The reserve covers an area of approximately 60 000ha, and was established to generate socio-economic benefits through wildlife-based tourism. The primary source for these benefits is through concessions to privately-owned safari lodges in the park, aimed at offering an exclusive wildlife experience to high-paying visitors. Approximately 35 lodges have been established in Madikwe and each is allowed one water point for game viewing. This results in spatially homogenous distribution of water points throughout the park.

The dry season water distribution was recorded during aerial game counts. To qualify the impact of water points on vegetation, changes in vegetation cover and structure over a period were determined through analysis of Landsat images. Landsat images at the end of the dry season, i.e. Jul/Aug for each year from 1999 to 2016 were analysed using ERDAS Imagine and GRASS GIS 7.0.4. The outcome of the image analysis indicated disturbance around temporary water holes and these disturbances, mostly the result of wildlife concentration, were qualified through vegetation surveys. The surveys measured compositional changes and impact – specifically browsing - along a gradient away from the water point. We could identify piospheres around water points, and the extent of these piospheres allowed us to qualify the sum of the impact of water points associated with lodges. Although Madikwe is primarily for economic development, it is important that the impact of extensive water provision in semi-arid systems be understood.

Twenty years of wildlife-powerline interaction monitoring and mitigating: balancing conservation and corporate costs

Samantha Page-Nicholson & Constant Hoogstad

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Generally, powerlines built in South Africa before 1990 were not subject to environmental impact assessments. This has resulted in thousands of kilometres of powerlines across South Africa that are dangerous to wildlife. In October 1996 the Eskom/Endangered Wildlife Trust Strategic Partnership was launched. This was undertaken to record all negative wildlife-energy infrastructure interactions, and further; to mitigate powerlines to prevent additional fatalities and reduce costs to Eskom. All incidents are recorded in a Central Incident Register (a first of its kind to record such interactions). The 20 year database has recorded over 2800 wildlife interactions and as of August 2016 the most heavily impacted species were the Blue Crane, *Anthropoides paradiseus* (1,194 collision-related mortalities), Cape Griffon, *Gyps coprotheres* (975 mortalities) and White-backed Vulture, *Gyps africanus* (404 mortalities). These incidents also affect the country's electricity supply grid, sometimes resulting in an unstable supply and high financial costs to Eskom due to power outage and damage to infrastructure. This unique partnership strikes a balance between mitigating high-risk powerlines to prevent re-occurrence of mortalities and financial costs of mitigating. Due to the nature of some incidents and the costs involved, not every incident is mitigated; rather powerlines that have a high risk of re-occurrence or mortalities are prioritized for mitigation. Multiple mitigation strategies/devices have been developed by the partnership including: bird-flight diverters, bird-friendly pole designs, and bird-guards, amongst others. During the last financial year (April 2015-April 2016) Eskom changed more than 1,215 poles to bird-friendly structures, insulated 63 transformers/strain poles, and fitted 724 spans of lines with bird flight diverters that amounted to more than 12,108 units.

Sustainable management of wildlife pests: The gerbil problem in balance?

Emil von Maltitz¹, Frikkie Kirsten¹, Lourens Swanepoel² & Mark Keith³

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³*Centre for Wildlife Management, University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa*

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It is estimated that rodents in commercial maize producing areas in South Africa damaged more than 54 000 ha of maize during the 2012/13 season. Rodent damage occurred during the planting stage in maize, groundnuts and soya, necessitating replanting. We intensively monitored crop fields, natural grazing areas and nature reserves in the Free State, North West and Mpumalanga Highveld during 2013-16, areas reported most severely affected by rodents. Abundance was determined through mark recapture, and habitat association determined through live and snap trapping. We investigated diet of rodents through stomach content and stable isotope analysis. We also investigated various control methods, ranging from chemical control, avian predation, and the feasibility of mammalian predation. The gerbils, *Gerbilliscus brantsii* and *G. leucogaster* were the dominant rodent species numerically and in terms of diversity in all the study areas. Pest rodent population ecology appears to be mediated through regional climate and local harvest wastage. We found that dressing maize seed with zinc phosphide was an effective method to minimise gerbil damage at planting, as well as minimising secondary poisoning. We also found that avian and mammalian predation can play a role in an ecologically based rodent pest management plan. Grazing after harvest and more effective harvesting practices can reduce crop wastage, while effective application and deployment of rodenticides can reduce gerbil damage to crop fields at planting.

Managing the relationship between mining and wildlife destinations - with specific reference to World Heritage Sites

Annemie de Klerk

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Mining has in many instances resulted in landscape changes, the production of large amounts of waste and pollution, the depletion of surface and groundwater resources, and the loss of habitats and wildlife. A literature review of State of Conservation Reports of World Heritage properties conducted by the researcher confirms that the threat from extractive industries is growing, particularly in Africa, where 40% of properties were included in 2012 on the List of World Heritage in Danger. The rapid expansion of mining developments in and around World Heritage Sites is therefore a growing concern, particularly in the light of recent studies confirming that large unexplored mineral wealth occurs in areas associated with unique natural beauty and unspoilt mountain landscapes. In support of expanding the mining cluster, South Africa will embark on an extensive infrastructural development plan, as well as putting actions in place to “address major constraints impeding growth of mining” (National Planning Commission, 2011). Potential conflict in land use between mining and wildlife destinations is therefore unavoidable.

Managing the relationship between mining, World Heritage Sites and wildlife destinations is therefore imperative. Findings from four in-depth international case reviews and research conducted in two case study areas in the Limpopo Province will be presented. The paper will conclude with key strategic factors to be applied towards managing a sustainable relationship between mining and wildlife destinations.

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (Herbivores)

Spatial ecology and habitat use of GPS fitted giraffe in the Kalahari region of South Africa

Francois Deacon & G Nico Smit

University of the Free State - Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences - Department Animal, Wildlife & Grassland Sciences, South Africa

Presenter: Francois Deacon, Department Animal, Wildlife & Grassland Sciences. PO Box 339, Bloemfontein 9300, +27 (0)51 401 3554, DeaconF@ufs.ac.za

The research project was conducted in the Khamab Kalahari Nature Reserve (KKNR) in the North West Province of South Africa. The area is situated in the Kalahari savanna and is 95,537.56 ha in size with an average annual rainfall < 333 mm.

The first objective was to assess the habitat selection and spatial ecology of giraffe species based on the effect of season, habitat resources (browse and water) and plant species composition. The second objective was to investigate the diet selection of giraffe in relation to browse availability, and how daily activities (feeding and non-feeding) change during seasons.

Results indicate that distribution patterns of giraffe were strongly influenced by environmental variables. With the aid of GPS collars it was established that the average distances travelled differ between seasons, lowest in autumn (5.05 km / day), highest in winter (5.75 km / day). Giraffes utilized an average home range of 206.0 km². In the wet, hot season (summer), giraffes frequented smaller areas (average 177 km²), while in the dry, cool season (winter) they extended their home range (average 245 km²). Giraffes also favoured and avoided specific areas. They preferred tree densities of 744 to 1 084 plants ha⁻¹, combined with a high (> 5 600) Total Evapotranspiration Tree Equivalent (ETTE ha⁻¹). *Acacia erioloba*, *Z. mucronata*, *B. albitrunca* and *A. mellifera* represented 93% of the giraffe diet, suggesting that giraffe are preferentially searching for them even if they are less available (36.2%) than other woody species.

Vegetation density reflects small ungulate refuge habitat from predation

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Small prey species face considerable predation pressure from large and small predators. Thus, the ability to avoid predation by some members of this predator guild is vital for their persistence. We investigated the value of dense vegetation as potential refuge habitats in reducing predation on small ungulates in a thicket landscape. Populations of bushbuck *Tragelaphus scriptus* and duiker *Sylvicapra grimmia* in Addo Elephant National Park experienced rapid population declines following the reintroduction of apex predators (lion *Panthera leo* and spotted hyaena *Crocuta crocuta*) in 2003. These declines were likely the result of combined predation from large and small predators. Using two additional apex predator reintroductions in the same ecosystem, along with multi-year camera trapping, we used population trends of bushbuck and duiker to assess if the recent apex predator reintroductions caused similar declines in small ungulate populations. The population trends of small ungulates following the three apex predator reintroductions differed and we propose that these varying responses by the small ungulates stem from differences in the vegetation density, and hence availability of refuge habitats, at each site. Using Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR), we measured vegetation density and found that population declines were less likely in sites with denser vegetation.

Hence, in thicket vegetation, small ungulates exposed to predation from both large and small predators will likely persist where such refuge habitats are plentiful. Vegetation density is known to decline with excessive herbivory but is expected to increase under some global change scenarios, and these dynamics, together with management actions around predators, will have profound consequences for the persistence of small ungulates.

Framing the Riverine Rabbit (*Bunolagus monticularis*); modelling camera trap data from the Klein Karoo

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Camera traps offer an effective method for the remote monitoring of rare and elusive species. In this study we explore the efficacy of camera traps deployed in different sampling arrays at detecting the presence of the rare riverine rabbit (*Bunolagus monticularis*) whose presence has been confirmed within the Sanbona Wildlife Reserve in the Klein Karoo. The first array was extensive and comprised 146 camera traps placed at 2 km intervals covering an area of 540 km². The second array was intensive with clusters of 5 camera traps placed within 15 ha areas, conforming to the mean home range size for the species and covering a total area of 108 km². The extensive array detected a total of 42 species but no riverine rabbits. By contrast the intensive array detected a total of 33 species and 57 independent recordings of the riverine rabbit. Occupancy analysis of detections from the intensive array revealed that the best predictor of riverine rabbit presence ($\Psi=0.5$) was the absence of hares (*Lepus saxatilis* and *Lepus capensis*) and proximity to degraded land. Our results confirm the usefulness of camera traps for surveying this rare mammal but only on a sampling array that aligns to the home range of the target species. Future research will explore the generality of the occupancy results by repeating the intensive array in two other localities with confirmed riverine rabbit presence. Together these findings represent an important step toward understanding the fine scale predictors of presence for one of the world’s rarest mammal species.

A viable tool for hybrid detection in wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus* and *C. gnou*)

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There exists a close evolutionary relationship between blue- and black wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus* and *C. gnou*), including a short time since speciation, a shared chromosome number and many morphological similarities. This close relationship makes hybridization possible and significantly complicates the process of hybrid identification, in view of the many shared morphological and underlying shared genetic characteristics. There is an urgent need to find a lasting solution to the hybridization controversy without eroding the remaining pool of genetic diversity in black wildebeest, since the latter species reached the brink of extinction between the late 1800s and early 1900s. We used a set of 25 microsatellite loci to genotype a total of 499 wildebeest, including pure blue, pure black and putative hybrid individuals. A statistical approach based on Bayesian analysis (as implemented in STRUCTURE software) was used to generate the admixture proportion for each individual in the sample set. Thresholds for purity were established based on the results for known pure animals, but also with guidance from published studies and an established screening program for blesbok/bontebok (*Damaliscus pygargus pygargus* and *D. p. phillipsi*) hybrids at the National Zoological Gardens of South Africa.

Results indicate that the approach used is effective in identifying hybrid individuals, but also suggest that levels of hybridization may be either (i) lower than previously estimated, or (ii) have been significantly reduced by generations of backcrossing with pure animals. Results are discussed with reference to the role of backcrossing in hybrid detection and management, the utility of simulations to model the persistence of introgression under different scenarios, and the need for stakeholders and conservation agencies to agree on implementation of our results for hybrid management.

Principles and ethics in wildlife management – a paradigm shift

Anti-furtive inspection techniques in conservation areas: case study of Chimanimani National Reserve

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The challenge of the administrators of conservation areas in Mozambique is to stop destructive actions created by community residents. Some of the actions implemented by the administrators include uninterrupted patrols with the application of methods and appropriate enforcement techniques aided by technology inclusive of the community and resource management initiatives. The analysis of anti-furtive techniques in conservation areas was carried out at Chimanimani National Reserve (RNC), with the intuition of bringing out the real reasons that contribute to the weakened application of anti-furtive techniques. To achieve the objective, bibliographic research was used, which involved collection of information from the existing scarce literature, to allow broadening the topic and give clear conception of the problem. The collection of the literature was made in technical person documents and experts working with inspection of material storage areas. After conducting consultation, the field work was done within the group in order to obtain data on the anti-stealth inspection. The results showed that lack of material resources such as adequate instruments, lack of well qualified human resources for this activity, corruption among the inspectors and the population around the conservation areas, advanced age of the greater part of the inspectors, deficient communication between the inspectors and the management, are the main causes of weakened inspection at RNC. Besides these main causes, the study revealed negligence of the administrators in training new inspectors recently admitted, strong friendship among the residents and inspectors, poor rotation among the inspectors of other reserves, lack of knowledge of the real cause and/or objectives of conservation among the inspectors, aligning with low scholarly level, but it was not determined if these factors had effects on the faults.

The use of permanent passageways in fences to accommodate warthog movement

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Common warthogs (*Phacochoerus africanus*) are known for their ability to damage and undermine agricultural fences, creating holes which allow previously excluded predators to gain access to livestock and game animals. This study investigated the use of two types of permanent passageways in fences to allow the movement of warthogs whilst potentially deterring predator movement. Four existing holes along an 800 m game fence on a mixed livestock and game farm were monitored with camera traps (trap days ranging from 188-430 per trap between December 2013 and July 2015) before and after the installation of permanent passageways.

The first type of passageway consisted of a steel frame with chains covering the opening, and the second of a steel frame with a wire mesh swing gate covering the opening. At two of the four holes the gate types were initially installed as open frames and subsequently as half structures as a conditioning period. After warthogs were observed to pass through the half structures, these were completed as full structures. The full chain gates were monitored for 32-260 days per trap, and the full swing gates for 27-93 days per trap. Warthogs were recorded to use both types of passageways, while black-backed jackals (*Canis mesomelas*) were observed to use full chain passageways on five occasions, and to turn around at the full wire mesh gateway on one occasion.

The results indicated that both types of permanent passage ways allow the movement of warthogs through pre-existing holes in fences. However, it is suggested that swing gates are monitored for a longer period of time to determine their efficiency at deterring predator movement.

Under what circumstances can wildlife farming benefit species conservation?

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Wild animals and their derivatives are traded worldwide. Consequent poaching has been a main threat to species conservation. As current interventions and law enforcement cannot circumvent the resulting extinction of species, an alternative approach must be considered. It has been suggested that commercial breeding can keep the pressure off wild populations, referred to as wildlife farming. During this review, it is argued that wildlife farming can benefit species conservation only if the following criteria are met: (i) the legal products will form a substitute, and consumers show no preference for wild-caught animals; (ii) a substantial part of the demand is met, and the demand does not increase due to the legalized market; (iii) the legal products will be more cost-efficient, in order to combat the black market prices; (iv) wildlife farming does not rely on wild populations for re-stocking; (v) laundering of illegal products into the commercial trade is absent. For most species encountered in the wildlife trade, these criteria are unlikely to be met and commercial breeding has the potential to have the opposite effect to what is desired for conservation. For some species, however, none of the criteria are violated, and wildlife farming can be considered a possible conservation tool as it may help to take the pressure off wild populations. For these species, future research should focus on the impact of legal products on the market dynamics, effective law enforcement that can prevent corruption and wildlife forensics that enable the distinction between captive-bred and wild-caught species.

Baboon management success? Can a shift in paradigm assist future management of baboons?

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Proactive baboon management on the Cape peninsula has been on-going since 1998 and aims to ensure a sustainable baboon population as well as managing baboon impacts on humans and their property. One of the key interventions funded by the City of Cape Town is the Baboon Monitoring Program with an annual budget of ten million rand. To date this program has never been evaluated externally. Here we present data on the first evaluation of this program undertaken by Baboon Matters Trust. We extracted three years of data from publicly available monthly reports of Human Wildlife Solutions, the service provider currently implementing the program. Our aim was to investigate whether removal of specific baboons identified as raiders resulted in a reduction of overall raiding by a troop. A second aim was to examine changes in home range size and population size after management interventions. Results showed that in 40% of cases removal of baboons identified as raiders resulted in a reduction of troop raiding, home ranges sizes relative to troop size have been significantly reduced when compared to home ranges size before management and adult sex ratios of

the Southern population are skewed in favour of female baboons. We conclude that the current management paradigm does not address the underlying cause of baboon human conflict and suggest alternative management options

Remotely operated virtual fences: a successful new approach to baboon management

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Current baboon management practices in Cape Town, using rangers with paintball markers, are labour intensive and expensive. Virtual Fencing (VF) is an alternative, cost effective strategy for deterring baboons from entering urban or agricultural spaces, particularly in remote terrain. HWS has recently developed a VF to control baboons from entering specific urban areas in the Western Cape. The VF is based on the principal of creating a "landscape of fear" which baboons are reluctant to cross, for fear of the consequences (predation, exposure to unpleasant stimuli) that might follow. The VF is comprised of hidden, waterproof, remotely operated, action stations which are capable of firing bearbanger flares and producing a selection of sounds, including predator calls, alarm calls and cries of animals in distress. The element of "fear" is increased by the temporal unpredictability of the system. Using a wide variety of stimuli adds to the fear, and reduces habituation. The system is operated remotely using a hand-held controller or smart phone. GPS radio-collared animals can be tracked in real time using relay stations and a gateway router to one's GSM network. This provides an early warning system via sms, or the internet, and allows remote activation of the fence from anywhere. The VF has been in operation outside Gordon's Bay since January with 100% success and saved 3,500 man hours in labour during its first three months of operation. This system can be modified to manage other damage causing animals, whilst the tracking component has great potential for research.

Tuesday, 20 September 2016

Invited Keynote address:

Large herbivore management and the concept of carrying capacity

Norman Owen-Smith

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More than three decades ago, Graeme Caughley asked "What is this thing called carrying capacity?" He claimed that "if left alone most populations converge to a steady density (ecological carrying capacity)..." But is this what we observe when large herbivores are left unmanaged in properties of varying sizes? Can we anticipate the density level that a wild ungulate will attain within a game ranch or protected area? The abundance level exhibited is largely an expression of habitat suitability, which depends on resources supplied, shelter from stress provided, and security from predation obtained. The features vary through time and over space. The optimal stocking level depends also on the objectives of the land owner or manager: maximizing productive offtake, accommodating most animals, or sustaining key resources. The quality of the forage produced during the growing season needs to be counterbalanced against the amount remaining to support animals during the dry season, and through bad years. I will illustrate how these concepts can be applied to both browsers and

grazers, aimed either at maximizing production or at fostering sustainability. A crucial factor is how plant populations respond to the grazing or browsing impacts of herbivores.

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (General)

The state of our mammals: how far have we come and where are we going?

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The results of the 2016 Red List revision for mammals of South Africa, Swaziland and Lesotho reveal that 17% of our mammals are threatened with extinction, compared to 19% in the previous assessment (2004). However, these summary statistics belie that of the ~30 genuine changes in conservation status recorded since 2004, 57% were uplistings (i.e. species have become more threatened). Why have we made no net progress over a decade of conservation effort? We argue that this is primarily due to the middling tendency of conservation science and practice: we are neither grappling with the broad scale drivers that cause habitat loss and degradation (such as human population growth, built environment expansion and hyper-consumerism) and the emerging threat of wildlife trafficking (consumer misinformation and socio-economic disparities); nor are we producing evidence for the effectiveness (or ineffectiveness) of interventions at local scales (c. 5% of scientific publications analysed provide experimental evidence). Ultimately our failure to do so undermines attempts to manage wildlife sustainably. Here we present a framework for mammal conservation research, based on the set of most severe threats occurring at different scales and the proposed interventions to tackle them. Key recommendations are broadening the sphere of research collaboration to include behavioural economists, social scientists and town planners, and to adjust funding mechanisms and incentives to stimulate research that produces conservation evidence to support effective practice.

Unravelling a Kalahari Desert food chain using stable isotopes, can it teach us anything new?

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Food chain dynamics are key to our understanding of ecosystem functioning and are considered a cornerstone of ecological theory. Considerable time and effort have been invested to study the diet of large terrestrial animals (>10kg), and in well studied ecosystems it might be perceived that little can be gained from further investigation. Here I present data that shows how the study of a large animal food chain in the Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park using stable isotope analysis can provide novel insights pertaining to the diet of both primary and secondary consumers. A total of 438 plant and animal samples were collected over two years and analysed for its stable carbon and nitrogen isotope ratios. Samples comprised of 55 plant leaf samples, 34 herbivore dung samples, 79 herbivore hair, feather and quill samples, and 270 lion (*Panthera leo*) whisker segments from 5 different lionesses. Gemsbok *Oryx gazelle* considered a grazer, should be re-considered as a mix-feeder in this system as grass only made up 58% of their average diet. This is in contrast to the supposedly mix-feeding eland

Tragelaphus oryx that have a low grass intake (avg = 19%).

At the secondary consumer level the stable isotope results revealed that lion utilize gemsbok and conventional grazers (blue wildebeest *Connochaetes taurinus* and/or red hartebeest *Alcelaphus buselaphus*) most. There is also an indication of specialization with one lioness covering significantly smaller isotopic niche space than the other four. These findings suggest that food chain studies using stable isotopes might provide new insights in other ecosystems as well.

The impact of DDT on the bone X-ray density and bone length of the House Sparrow in designated areas of the Limpopo Province

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The use of DDT (dichloro-diphenyl-trichloroethane) is controversial. The question of its effectiveness as an insecticide has to be weighed against its impact on the environment. DDE, a metabolite of DDT, has been reported to decrease bone density in crocodiles and produce bone asymmetry in birds. The impact of DDT on bone development in House Sparrows has been assessed. Birds were collected from six sites in Limpopo Province, South Africa: two of them were last sprayed 30 years ago (YA); two were last sprayed 5 years ago; and two were sprayed recently (2015). The density of the femur and the total length of the femur, tibia and tarsal bones were analysed by X-ray μ -CT tomography. Non-significant difference between the total lengths of the left and right legs ($P > 0.496$) of any of the birds from the sites was found. There was also no significant difference ($P > 0.167$) between the lengths of the left and right legs between male and female birds. In one of the sites sprayed 30 years ago (Tshakuma), bone density analysis showed that the birds had a significant difference ($P < 0.037$) compared to birds collected from other sites. Bone density also differed significantly ($P < 0.029$) between the one 5 years ago sprayed site (Mangondi) and the recently sprayed site, Lefule. None of the other comparisons were significantly different. The limited effect of DDT on bone lengths and density in the House Sparrow suggests that the bones were not detrimentally affected by the prevailing concentrations in the environment.

The farmer's friend: The success story of Wakkerstroom's Secretarybirds

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The diet of a raptor population tells us which prey is caught. Diet studies also help us understand how prey is linked to local habitats, and helps inform us on how to manage these habitats for such a population. The IUCN recently upgraded the Secretarybird's (*Sagittarius serpentarius*) conservation status to Vulnerable due to an unconfirmed reduction in the Secretarybird's distribution. The Tshwane University of Technology (Department of Nature Conservation) and BirdLife South Africa therefore initiated the Wakkerstroom Secretarybird Project to investigate the diets of birds nesting near agriculture lands and wetlands in the Highveld grasslands of Wakkerstroom. Prey remains in the form of regurgitated pellets were collected from 16 nests. One hundred and thirteen pellets were processed and identified to the lowest taxa possible. The diets in the two habitats were almost similar (Multi-Response Permutation Procedure, $T = 1.05$, $P = 0.92$), but showed more prey heterogeneity than expected ($A = -0.03$). The most dominant prey species, in terms of abundance, were Brown Locust (*Locustana pardalia*) (36%), beetles (Coleoptera) (19%), Rinkhals (*Hemachatus heamachatus*) (3%) and Vlei Rat (*Otomys irroratus*) (2%). Brown Locust and beetles associated with both agricultural

lands and wetlands, whereas Rinkhals and Vlei Rat associated predominantly with wetlands. The success of these birds can therefore be ascribed to having both habitats available allowing them to hunt this particularly varied diet in different spaces. Due to their association with wetlands and agricultural lands, management strategies to keep this species on local farmer's land can now be put into place.

Guidelines for habitat management: The influence of slope on population expansion of *Euphorbia clivicola* R.A. Dyer. A Case Study

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Topographical factors such as slope, aspect and position play a significant role in plant survival and community arrangement. *Euphorbia clivicola* is a rare and critically endangered plant species in the Limpopo Province, South Africa. This species tend to grow on northern slopes that are earmarked for urban development within its distribution area. The aim of this research was to assess the significance of slope on population structure. The occupied habitat was stratified into three positions: top slope, middle slope and bottom slope. Population structure and density of the plants were documented. *Euphorbia clivicola* plants gradually decreased in canopy size as the slope gradient decrease (from top to bottom). Thus the significance of slope on population structure is that slope influences propagule dispersal and ultimately population structure through surface water runoff. Density was inversely proportional to canopy size, which suggests that colonisation of sites by *E. clivicola* is influenced by slope gradient. Conservators should discourage development on the northern aspects of habitats occupied by *E. clivicola*, as it will negatively affect the relief site of the plant.

The diet selection of extralimital giraffe in Albany Thicket vegetation within the Little Karoo region of South Africa

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Herbivore diet assessments provide the basis for understanding resource and habitat requirements of species, and are particularly crucial for extralimital species being introduced despite little being known regarding their suitability for the receiving environments.

Due to popularity for tourism, South African giraffes, *Giraffa camelopardalis giraffa*, are continuously being introduced into Thicket areas within the Little Karoo region of the Western Cape. This study evaluated the diet selection of two giraffe populations present on two game reserves, namely Kareesbos Private Game Reserve and Tsumkwe Private Game Reserve. Diet selection, as well as the level of browsing, was observed by means of direct observations occurring every five minutes from sunrise to sunset. Sixteen plant species were consumed, with *Pappaea capensis* and *Portulacaria afra* forming the bulk of the diet in Kareesbos throughout all seasons. *Acacia karoo* and *Grewia robusta* dominated the diet in Tsumkwe during spring and the remaining seasons respectively. Browsing heights were similar on both game reserves, with giraffes browsing mostly at shoulder height (level 3) and below (level 2).

Results indicate that these giraffes are able to take advantage of forage available in ecosystems outside their natural ranges. Low levels of feeding display possible niche overlaps with other present browsers, which may result in increased competition (intra- and interspecific) for food when it becomes

limited. Long term ecological monitoring of extralimital populations and appropriate management procedures are therefore required to avoid the displacement and degradation of indigenous fauna and flora within the Little Karoo, and possible mortalities amongst the giraffe populations.

The ecological impact of elephant herbivory on vegetation of Atherstone Collaborative Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa

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African elephants (*Loxodonta Africana*) cause serious damage to important tree species, and certain species such as *Senegalia* species and Marula (*Sclerocarya birrea*) are often targeted. High levels of plant utilization may compromise the viability of some woody plant populations, leading to vegetation changes coupled with a possible loss of species and/or structural diversity. Various tree nesting raptors are potentially susceptible to the loss of nesting sites due to elephant impact. If not managed properly, an overpopulation of elephants often leads to environmental degradation. Such degradation could lead to a loss in ecosystem function, which not only implies a loss in ecosystem productivity and resilience, but also the need for ecosystem restoration. Here we look, using the standard Braun-Blanquet method, at the impact of elephant herbivory on the rest of the biodiversity on the ACNR. We investigated the interactions between elephants and vegetation. Vegetation changes around long term monitoring plots were assessed and comparison was made between 2004 and 2014. This study has indicated that elephant damage constituted a significant threat to the Marula population on the reserve. Elephant damage was mostly in the form of bark stripping of tree bark. The wood borer infestation was evident after debarking damage caused by elephants. This has led to large-scale changes in demographic structure of Marula, mainly characterized by a reduction in the number of larger trees and a simultaneous increase of size classes susceptible to fire. Furthermore, demonstrates that increasing elephant impact is a powerful mechanism in shaping the structure and composition of Marula woodlands in the ACNR. To prevent the extinction of Marula trees in the reserve, it is imperative that the reduction of the elephant population be addressed. This will ensure the conservation of the Red Bush-willow veld type, of which Marula trees form an integral part.

Adapting Wildlife Management in the light of global change

The managed metapopulation approach for Cheetah conservation: A suitable technique outside of South Africa?

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Cheetah (*Acinonyx jubatus*) numbers have decreased across Africa at 2.26% per annum over the past century. Cheetahs occur in 29 subpopulations that have limited connectivity between them. Sixteen populations contain less than 30 animals and, with limited natural dispersal between them, are not viable in the long-term. In South Africa, cheetah numbers are increasing at 2.17% per annum - largely due to the managed metapopulation approach adopted for cheetahs across 53 fenced reserves which has increased both numbers and range. In these reserves, adult cheetahs and cubs have higher survival rates than on unfenced systems in Namibia and the Tanzania. Metapopulation cheetahs occur at some of the highest densities in Africa. Sixteen reserves in countries to the north of South Africa have recently been fenced to reduce human-wildlife conflict. Four of these have requested cheetahs from the metapopulation for restoration, providing opportunities to explore new avenues for the managed metapopulation approach. We acknowledge the limitations of the South African model: it is

expensive; 7% of relocated cheetahs die; and natural landscape processes are not always at play. The less managed approach adopted outside of South Africa places a strong emphasis on natural gene flow through the establishment of corridors between conservation areas promoting natural recolonisation. Here we contrast the opposing conservation techniques and their efficacy in light of human population growth and economic development. We discuss whether the managed metapopulation approach will be suitable for creating safe space or simulating gene flow for cheetahs elsewhere in Africa.

Environmental Leadership: Exploring environmental dissonance involving natural resource consumption and ecosystem degradation

Thomas L Tochterman

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As the corporate world, communities, and individuals become more globalized with increased demands on natural resources, a new emphasis on environmental leadership including a new pragmatic environmental ethos is needed to meet certain basic human needs of future generations. The research problem addressed was the lack of knowledge concerning how environmental cognitive dissonance influences consumption related to inefficient resource utilization and ecosystem degradation. The purpose of this study was to provide an understanding of the breadth and depth of the environmental cognitive dissonance among visitors to the Kruger National Park. The research questions addressed antecedents to the development, manifestation, and mitigation of environmental dissonance? This qualitative case study was designed for a purposeful sample of 12 participants visiting the Kruger National Park, South Africa. Data were collected via structured interviews, field observations, and questionnaires then analyzed using a data spiral and cross case analysis. The dominant findings suggested that: (a) awareness of personal values, culture, and perceptions toward the environment were responsible for basic attitudes toward the environment and consumption: (b) wasteful habits, excessive consumption, and market influences were juxtaposed with nostalgic/episodic memories and deep thoughts about personal consumptive habits; and (c) an interactive multi-sensory experience in a pristine and wild environment changed perceptions and values toward ecosystems and ecosystem preservation. The results of this study could help individuals and organizations to develop a new understanding of consumptive behaviour and a new consumer ethos of stewardship and environmental leadership; one that inspires healthy and sustainable ecosystems.

Fear factor: the effects of a varying predation pressure and vegetation structure on prey species in a novel wetland ecosystem

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Prey animals often forage in environments in which resource patches vary in predation risk. In this 'landscape of fear', an animal constantly has to trade-off food and safety in its movements. Changes in vegetative structure and composition can modify this 'landscape of fear' by increasing or decreasing cover for prey. Certain species may thrive in this changed vegetation, outcompeting those that struggle to adapt, thereby altering the effects of predation on prey diversity and community structure.

Novel ecosystems can be interesting field laboratories where ecological theory can be investigated. One such novel ecosystem is the secondary area of Sasol's plant in Secunda, where recently, one of the highest serval (*Leptailurus serval*) densities was ever recorded. After initiating studies to investigate the small mammal density and diversity in high predation areas, we then implemented giving-up density (GUD) experiments to investigate the effects of varying predation pressures and vegetation structure on prey foraging behaviour. Initial results indicate that two rodent species (*Rhabdomys pumilio* and *Mastomys natalensis*) are the most dominant on the site, while the vlei rat (*Otomys irroratus*), is less common. We found that there was a positive effect of vegetation cover on GUD's, with higher foraging rates in densely vegetated areas compared to increased vigilance and reduced GUD in sparsely covered sites. Our results suggest that variations in vegetation cover can be an important factor shaping the landscape of fear, which can in turn play an important role in small mammal diversity.

Stakeholder perceptions of climate change impacts on wildlife resources: implications for wildlife management in the Middle Zambezi Biosphere Reserve, Zimbabwe

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Wildlife and human communities in savanna ecosystems are under increasing threat from multiple stressors particularly the dual impact of human wildlife interactions and climate change. The study adopted a mixed methods approach to investigate local community perceptions of impacts of climate change on wildlife resources and human communities within a biosphere reserve. Secondary climate records (1980-2015) and Participatory Rural Appraisal were used to collect data from Nyamakate Resettlement Area within the Middle Zambezi Biosphere Reserve, Zimbabwe, between April and August 2015. Survey questions were related to local people's perceptions of climate change, socio-economic and bio-physical impacts of climate change, coping and adaptation strategies. Data were analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Survey respondents reported that conditions were drier and rainfall timing was becoming less predictable. Analysis of monthly rainfall data for the climate period 1980 to 2015 indicates that total rainfall across seasons has significantly changed and that timing and transitions of seasons has been highly variable. Significant changes in the intra-seasonal rainfall distribution, including longer dry periods within rainy seasons may be contributing to the perceived decrease in rainfall thereby compromising forage availability and food security. Human communities at the wildlife-agriculture interface adopt coping strategies such as illegal harvesting of wildlife resources and habitat encroachment for pastures and cultivation. This exacerbates human-wildlife conflicts due to increasing overlap of habitats and interaction among livestock, wildlife and humans. Our results indicate the need for fine scale climate information to develop adaptive wildlife management practices and mitigation strategies to enhance the management of socio-ecological systems in biosphere reserves.

The evolution of wild dog (*Lycaon pictus*) metapopulation management in South Africa

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In South Africa, restoration of African wild dogs (*Lycaon pictus*) to areas where they were previously extirpated has been achieved through a managed metapopulation approach for over 18 years. This has been accomplished through artificially mediated dispersal and colonisation across a network of small, isolated and fenced reserves, coordinated by the Wild Dog Advisory Group of South Africa

(WAG-SA) and the KwaZulu-Natal Wild Dog Advisory Group (KZNWAG), comprised of a variety of stakeholders. The initial goal of the metapopulation was to increase the population and expand the range of wild dogs in South Africa through a series of reintroductions. At the outset, metapopulation managers had limited experience in assessing site suitability and long-term landowner willingness. In recent years, space for new introductions has become increasingly limited resulting in novel challenges requiring fundamental changes in management approach.

Currently, reintroductions are based on criteria used to assess site suitability that prioritise key areas for wild dogs. These criteria are based on years of experience accumulated by stakeholders from WAG-SA and KZNWAG. This has culminated in a revised managed metapopulation strategy focused on maintaining the current population, while also generating evidence to refine the efficacy of population management tools. The success of the programme can largely be attributed to clearly defined goals supported by long-term and ongoing commitment from key role players. Metapopulation management continues to compete with other acute conservation management concerns, and needs to be more widely embraced to support the conservation of wild dogs and other similar species in South Africa.

Managing to save the rhino in the Limpopo Province?

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The Limpopo Province falls within the Central Bushveld- and the Lowveld Bioregion which make suitable habitat for black (*Diceros bicornis*) and especially white (*Ceratotherium simum*) rhino. From 2006 to 2016, 577 white rhino were lost as a result of poaching. Another concern is the decline of rhino numbers on privately owned land due to the high security risk. With most of Limpopo's rhinos on privately owned land, support from the management authority is crucial to conserve these species. The demand to keep rhino in smaller camps for security reasons has increased but zonation of land according to the Limpopo Conservation Plan, might have restrictions with regard to dividing the land into smaller camps. Several directorates are involved in wildlife management e.g. issuing of permits, compliance and enforcement and biodiversity management. The effectiveness of these as species conservation measures deserves scrutiny. The status of rhino populations in the Limpopo province is investigated and the responsibilities of the management authority are scrutinized with the aim to improve on these to conserve the species in the province. This paper also provides a short analysis on the progress made in the last 20 years, with regard to conservation of the white and black rhino in South Africa.

The spatial and dietary ecology of baboons in conflict with sheep farmers in the Karoo

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In the central Karoo livestock farmers perceive losses to jackals (*Canis mesomelas*) and caracals (*Caracal caracal*) as a major threat to the sustainability of their livelihoods. Recently farmers reported that baboons (*Papio ursinus*) have added to their losses by targeting sheep. Direct observations of baboons depredating sheep are rare and habituating persecuted primates is impracticable. Consequently, we indirectly quantify the extent and severity of the problem using 77 farmers' interviews, while providing the first study of Karoo baboon ecology, using camera traps and GPS collars (monitoring five troops) to determine spatial predictors of baboon presence on farmlands. We estimated body condition and monthly diet (using isotopes) from 50 baboons culled in conflict areas.

Our results suggest that the conflict is restricted to farms with mountain and riverine habitat where baboons are more common. Indeed, only a third of interviewed farmers reported baboon problems with losses ranging from few individuals to as high as 50% of lambs. Karoo baboons are significantly lighter, living in smaller troops with a larger home range than their more mesic counterparts suggesting that the Karoo is limited with respect to resources. Interestingly, interviewees report most attacks during drought episodes, when resources are scarce. Isotope results also show a marked seasonal shift in baboon diet that may be associated with rainfall, but further investigation is needed to identify sheep as a potential fall back food. We discuss factors that may have promoted sheep predation by baboons in the Karoo and the importance of alternative management methods.

A scenario supposition of the effects on ecological systems by hydraulic fracturing in the Nama Karoo, South Africa

Jan Arkert

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This study focuses on the potential effects and impacts to biodiversity and ecosystem services due to hydraulic fracturing in the Nama Karoo. Fracking has become a highly contested issue internationally and no less so in South Africa, where applications are being considered by the government to permit three international companies to proceed with shale gas extraction.

With no domestic experience of fracking in South Africa a literature research of data emanating from the USA was conducted to evaluate the extraction process. Documented environmental impacts and effects on biodiversity and ecosystem services in the USA have been used to develop this scenario supposition of potential effects in the Nama Karoo biome. A qualitative study method was used to identify and evaluate existing biotic and abiotic systems within the biome. Habitat fragmentation and edge effects, the introduction of alien species, pollution of water resources and utilisation of wildlife are all recognised as being potentially affected by the proposed industrialisation of the Nama Karoo.

The potential habitat restrictions and influences on foraging behaviour of aardvark *Orycteropus afer*, are used to illustrate the potential impact that fracking may have on individual species, and by extension, prevailing ecosystem services.

Wednesday, 21 September 2016

Invited Keynote address:

History and future of large carnivore conservation research and management in South Africa

Michael GL (Gus) Mills

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As apex predators large carnivores play an important role in ecosystems, but also often come into conflict with humans. Consequently most are threatened and all need conservation attention. Therefore they have attracted a large amount of attention in conservation research and management. I will sketch the history of large carnivore research and management in South Africa over the last 50 years and discuss the importance of long-term studies and research in different ecosystems for understanding the role of large carnivores in regulating prey populations. I will also examine the unusual conditions under which large carnivores exist in South Africa, where so many have been introduced into small fenced reserves. I will discuss what are regarded as the important questions and management strategies for large carnivores currently in place, and whether these are necessarily providing the best information, and yielding the best results. I will also discuss the philosophical principles of large carnivores and biodiversity.

Spotting changes? A national leopard monitoring plan for South Africa

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Rigorous population data are essential for informing conservation and management of threatened species. These data are difficult to obtain for wide ranging, cryptic species, such as large carnivores, which can lead to inappropriate management of these charismatic and ecologically vital species. Leopards (*Panthera pardus*) are one such species; despite being widely distributed across South Africa, there is growing evidence to suggest that leopard populations are declining significantly across broad areas of their range. Effective management of leopard populations is impeded by the lack of robust population data across much of the leopard's range. We therefore propose a national framework for monitoring leopards in South Africa. Robust population density estimates should be produced using camera trap surveys at selected monitoring sites within each province. This intensive monitoring would be complemented by broader scale monitoring using occupancy analysis, as well as harvest composition and catch per unit effort data in provinces where legal killing of leopards occurs. Both forms of monitoring would aim to track leopard population changes over time and inform conservation management of the efficacy of attempts to mitigate threats to leopards, such as the illegal skin trade. Robust monitoring should also guide management of damage-causing animals and trophy hunting. We believe that the establishment and implementation of such a monitoring framework is essential to the long-term survival of South Africa's leopard population. In this presentation, we discuss issues relating to the design, implementation, and effectiveness of South Africa's leopard monitoring framework.

Population density trends and threats to leopards outside protected areas

Samual T Williams, Kathryn S Williams & Russell A Hill

Primate and Predator Project, South Africa

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Large carnivores such as leopards (*Panthera pardus*) are becoming increasingly endangered, and the importance of land outside of protected areas to carnivore conservation is becoming clearer. Data on the population trends and threats to leopards is imperative to inform sustainable management of the species, but there is a dearth of long-term studies in these areas. We present the first systematic long-term study of the population trends and threats to leopards in the Soutpansberg mountain range, Limpopo Province, South Africa. We used camera traps and spatially explicit capture recapture analysis to determine leopard population density at regular intervals. We also fitted eight leopards with GPS collars for 15 months to determine the threats to the population. Leopard population density declined by 65% over approximately seven and a half years. The number of adult female leopards and cubs photographed in each survey decreased over time, while the number of adult males photographed remained stable. The main causes of leopard mortality were illegal human activity such as snaring, shooting, and poisoning. In light of these data we initiated a community engagement programme with the aim of reducing the level of anthropogenic mortality of leopards and mitigating and human-wildlife conflict. We will continue to monitor the population to assess the effectiveness of these interventions.

The cat is out of the bag: a preliminary review of the scale of the illegal leopard skin trade in southern Africa

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Across southern Africa, large numbers of leopards (*Panthera pardus*) are killed for their skins. These are used by members of the Nazareth Baptist (Shembe) Church, and other African cultures, in ceremonial attire. Capture-recapture and questionnaire surveys undertaken at Shembe gatherings estimate that 10 000 - 15 000 leopard skins are currently in circulation among Shembe followers and that between 1500 - 2500 leopards are harvested each year to fuel the demand for skins. Despite being listed under South Africa's Threatened or Protected Species regulations the illegal skin trade is likely having a devastating effect on South Africa's leopard population, and potentially leopard populations more widely. Interviews with skin traders reveal that they can no longer acquire sufficient skins from KwaZulu-Natal – these populations may already be too depleted – and that most of their stock is now sourced from neighbouring countries. This is consistent with our preliminary genetic analysis of a subset of skin samples that suggests that while some traded leopard skins originate in South Africa (primarily from Zululand and areas adjoining the Kruger National Park), the majority can be traced to southern Zimbabwe and Mozambique. The donation of approximately 13 000 highly realistic faux leopard skin capes as part of Panthera's Furs for Life Project has undoubtedly reduced demand for skins among Shembe followers. However, it is imperative that we continue to investigate the scale of the skin trade and pinpoint the leopard populations most affected by illegal harvesting in order to enable conservation agencies to focus enforcement in the most critical areas.

The dilemma of lions (*Panthera leo*) in small reserves and consequences for management

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With the continuing establishment of protected areas in South Africa, the number of free-ranging, reintroduced lion (*Panthera leo*) populations is also increasing. Although introduced for ecological and tourism incentives, lions pose several management challenges in small (<1,000 km²) reserves. Protected areas have experienced varying scales of impacts by reintroduced lions, providing a unique opportunity to further our scientific understanding of lion behaviour and effective management. In large open systems, ecological and lion social factors result in fluctuating lion populations. These mechanisms break down in smaller reserves where managers are forced to actively manage increasing lion populations to stabilize their effect on other species, particularly key prey. Current management options are costly and raise uncertainties, requiring further study. This research is comparing grouping behaviour, related predator-prey outcomes, and vital rates of lions across 36 reserves/national parks in South Africa. These reserves vary in size (70 km² - 19,500 km²), lion population structure and management regimes. Accumulated sightings and spatial data indicate differences in lion grouping behaviour. The data reflect that lions grouped more intensely with other known individuals within reserves with more than one pride. Adult male(s) and pride(s) grouped more with each other when cubs were present in a pride. These initial results demonstrate the importance of both territoriality and cub defence as driving forces behind grouping behaviour in lions, and that this behaviour can be affected by their population structure in an area. Our data will be used to highlight and develop best practice management guidelines for lions on smaller reserves.

Aging traits and sustainable trophy hunting of African lions

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Trophy hunting plays an important role in wildlife conservation globally, yet excessive hunting is contributing to species declines, especially for large carnivores. Using African lions (*Panthera leo*) as a case study, we tested criteria for an age-based approach for sustainably regulating hunting. Simulation models suggest that sustainable hunting may be achieved by restricting offtakes to male lions old enough to have reared a cohort of offspring. Using photos of 228 known-age males from ten sites across Africa, we measured change in ten phenotypic traits with age and found four age classes with distinct characteristics: 1-2.9 years, 3-4.9 years, 5-6.9 years, and ≥ 7 years. We tested the aging accuracy of professional hunters and inexperienced observers before and after training on aging. Before training, hunters accurately aged more lion photos (63%) than inexperienced observers (48%); after training, both groups improved (67-69%). Hunters overestimated 22% of lions <5 years as 5-6.9 years (unsustainable offtake) but only 4% of lions <5 years as ≥ 7 years (sustainable offtake). Due to the lower aging error for males ≥ 7 years, we recommend 7 years as a practical minimum age threshold for trophy hunting male lions. Results indicate that age-based hunting is feasible for sustainably managing threatened and economically significant species such as the lion, but must be guided by rigorous training, strict monitoring of compliance and error, and be supported by conservative quotas. Our study furthermore demonstrates methods for identifying traits to age individuals, information that is critical for estimating demographic parameters underlying management and conservation of age-structured species.

Age and sex identification from digital 3D models of lion paws using geometric morphometrics

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Assessing animal population trends in space and time represents the keystone of any conservation, management and research strategies. In the absence of direct observations, tracks offer a non-invasive low-cost approach to gain information on elusive species such as certain carnivores. However, monitoring species through their tracks is controversial due to unreliable recording techniques limited to two-dimensions, manipulator bias, substrate variation and subjective identification of the age, sex and/or individual. Furthermore, it is still uncertain whether some species possess foot anatomy that is complex enough to provide such information. The objective of this research is to analyse the size and shape of lion (*Panthera leo*) paws and to describe their variation in terms of age and sex. Using digital close-range three-dimensional (3D) photogrammetry, we sampled a total of 40 front left and 41 hind left lion paws belonging to 45 different individuals from both sex and three age classes (juvenile, sub-adult and adult). Size and shape variables were extracted from the paws by means of landmark-based geometric morphometrics using 20 fixed landmarks, and 130 curve- and 130 surface-sliders semi-landmarks. The landmark coordinates were superimposed through a Generalized Procrustes Analysis. Centroid size and procrustes coordinates were then used in a Linear Discriminant Analysis with jack-knifed prediction to assess accuracy for age and sex identification. For both front and hind paws, the accuracy of prediction reached 100% for the identification of the combination age-sex. Analysing the intrinsic properties of the paws will lead to a better understanding of the tracks they produce.

Wildlife Management Research - enhancing scientific knowledge base and/or policy development (carnivores & other)

Trends in Crocodile populations in the Olifants and Letaba Rivers, Limpopo Province, outside the Kruger National Park

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Significant declines in crocodile *Crocodylus niloticus* populations have been reported in the Olifants River in the past, both at the Loskop Dam in Mpumalanga and in the Olifants Gorge, Kruger National Park. The drivers behind these declines are complex and poorly understood, but include factors such as agro-industrial water and sediment pollution, dam-building, human encroachment into crocodile habitat, direct persecution, poaching and disease. The Olifants is assessed in Limpopo as two sub-catchments: The Olifants main-stem from the Loskop Dam down to the Kruger National Park boundary at Phalaborwa, and the Groot-Letaba from the Tzaneen Dam to the Kruger National Park boundary. Both catchments were surveyed in 2012 and 2015 by means of helicopter-based aerial censuses. The results of these surveys are presented here. Trends in the two sub-catchments were very different. Adult observation levels were found to be stable in the Olifants River sub-catchment with a slight decrease of 0.56 %, and a moderate increase in smaller size classes of 20.48 %. A dramatic, steep decline of 79.15 % was however observed in the Letaba River population, this being primarily focused in the area of the Letaba Ranch Nature Reserve and on adult animals (83.15 % decline). This does not reflect local migration into the Kruger National Park and it is proposed that this decline may be related to increased game poaching pressure and subsequent poisoning of poached carcasses that may be scavenged by crocodiles.

Habitat use and predator influence on honey badgers in iSimangaliso Wetland Park, South Africa

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Change in both land use and land cover brings about adverse effects on wildlife. The effects of land use change on many elusive mesocarnivores are poorly known. In addition to habitat transformation, the presence and habitat use of mesocarnivores can be driven by the distribution of large predators. Consequently, we investigated the occurrence of the relatively poorly known honey badger (*Mellivora capensis*) in iSimangaliso Wetland Park (IWP, St. Lucia, South Africa). Although the IWP is a protected area there are areas of forestry plantations (agroforestry) on its Western Shores, while areas on its Eastern Shores and Western Shores have been rehabilitated to natural vegetation. We used single-season camera trap data from a grid of 118 trap stations for 24 days. Average estimated occupancy of honey badger was 0.38 ± 0.08 and detection probability of 0.12 ± 0.03 , with a naïve occupancy estimate of 0.25. Distance to water and higher number of trees in the plantations were positively associated with honey badger occupancy. Leopard (*Panthera pardus pardus*) presence had a negative effect on honey badger detections while spotted hyena (*Crocuta crocuta*) presence was positively related to honey badger detections. Our findings showed that leopards are suggested as predators of the honey badger, while hyenas are cohabitant species with honey badger. We showed that the higher occurrence of honey badgers in plantations is linked to the beekeeping practices in patches of *Eucalyptus* trees. This suggests that the modified habitats, in comparison to native vegetation, support higher honey badger populations in the IWP.

Logistic population growth and vital rates of African wild dogs (*Lycaon pictus*) in Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park, KZN: patterns and implications

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The long-term population growth and vital rates of African wild dogs (*Lycaon pictus*) in Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park (HiP) in KZN are presented here and compared to larger populations. Wild dogs in HiP have been extensively monitored for 36 years, providing a high-resolution dataset. We found logistic growth with a mean annual growth rate of 5%, although growth rate was not correlated with population size. This suggests that the population has reached carrying capacity, likely due to a decrease in resource acquisition associated with increased intraspecific competition. Pup survival is the highest reported for the species. Moreover, pup survival to adulthood and sex-specific survival rates reflect those of a high-density population. However, the density of wild dogs in HiP ranged from 0.22 – 8.26 dogs/100km² (mean = 2.88 ± 0.38) over the 36 year study, falling in line with a medium-high density wild dog population. Temporal patterns of litter size, fecundity, probability of dominance, sex bias, pack size and reproductive success were similar to those found for a medium density wild dog population. These results suggest that demographic patterns of wild dogs in this enclosed system are synonymous with medium-high density free-roaming populations as in northern Botswana and Selous, Tanzania. This is likely due to initial population augmentation in the first half of the study yet with decreased input this population has expanded and maintained itself. Overall, these results highlight that small, enclosed populations can function naturally which is apparent in the long-term stability of this population and its ability to self regulate.

Spotted hyena (*Crocuta crocuta*) habitat use across a landuse gradient in western Zimbabwe

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Globally, increased human populations have caused loss of habitat for numerous species. It has led to a decline in populations of large carnivore species such as spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*) and their prey. Furthermore, it has caused increased domestic stock predation and hence human-wildlife conflicts near conservation areas. We conducted camera trap surveys with 3600 trap-days in three land management units (Protected Area (PA), conservancy with hunting, and ranch with livestock and wildlife farming) in western Zimbabwe during the dry and wet seasons of 2014-2015. We modelled habitat characteristics, potential major prey species and other disturbance factors under occupancy modelling approach to quantify the habitat use of hyenas. Habitat use (occupancy) was positively influenced by clay soil while detection probability of hyenas increased with prey species detection, teak (*Baikiaea plurijuga*) and human settlements during the wet season. Habitat use was positively influenced by clay soil and wild prey while detection probability of hyenas increased with wild prey species, livestock and PA in the dry season. We observed increased detection probability of hyenas with livestock detection, an indication of potential human wildlife conflict. Increased habitat use and detection probability was mainly attributed to high availability of wild prey found in the PA. High habitat

use in areas with clay soils indicated preference to denning sites. We concluded that land use and wild prey influenced habitat use by hyenas and management priorities should focus on improving habitats for prey.

Impacts of urbanization on the distribution, diet and health of the Cape clawless otter, *Aonyx capensis*, in the Western Cape, South Africa

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Globally, the expansion of coastal cities has impacted negatively on freshwater and marine ecosystems - primarily through habitat loss, fragmentation and pollution. Top predators within these systems are particularly vulnerable due to their greater space requirements and higher risk of bioaccumulation of pollutants. In the Western Cape, South Africa, the Cape clawless otter, *Aonyx capensis*, is now the top predator in many freshwater ecosystems, and is listed as Near Threatened as a result of the rapid degradation of freshwater ecosystems. Here, we explore the effects of urbanization on the habitat use, diet and pollution levels of otters living on the Cape Peninsula, South Africa. Both occupancy and Maxent models suggest that otters do not avoid urban areas, and are more frequently detected in transformed lowland freshwater systems close to marine protected areas. Otter diet within protected areas consisted of marine fish and crustaceans, whereas in transformed areas, otter diet was diverse and included more exotic freshwater prey species. Roadkilled otters showed signs of accumulation of PCB's in liver tissue suggesting that despite otters being adaptable generalists, their dependence on polluted freshwater systems may have long term health impacts. This study provides valuable insights into the urban conservation measures required to ensure the survival of a top predator at the land-sea interface.

Using technology-based data collection and wildlife crime analysis to combat poaching: a case study at Balule Nature Reserve

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International wildlife crime is a rapidly rising threat to biodiversity that creates huge challenges to conservation managers. This is especially so in South Africa, where illegal trade in rhino horn has led to the poaching of >5 000 rhinos since 2008 and law enforcement interventions continue to have low success rates. Despite massive investments by state and private rhino owners, as well as numerous law enforcement measures to protect rhinos, the poaching continues, and managers are being forced to devise novel methods to secure their animals. Here we present a data driven approach to anti-poaching security that uses a combination of technology and wildlife crime analysis to better use limited resources available to protected area managers. "Cmore" is a CSIR developed technology that allows field rangers to collect poaching related data using a smart phone application that doubles as a GPS tracking mechanism to record patrol routes. Data collected using Cmore are entered into standard GIS or spreadsheet software where basic analytical techniques are used to assess the effectiveness of ranger patrols at preventing poaching and identify ways to better use such ranger resources. Standard criminology theory adapted to wildlife crime issues, which has been shown to improve the rates of successful wildlife crime prosecutions in Uganda, is used to assist with this process. By implementing a standardised, real time approach to patrol data collection, law enforcement operations have the ability to maximise their command and control efficiency for deployment and response.

Prevalence and diversity of tick-borne pathogens in caracals and jackals in human-modified landscapes

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The increasing emergence of infectious diseases may be the result of rapid global change influencing ecological stability. Despite the importance of disease as a conservation threat, there is a paucity of baseline research on the epidemiology of pathogens occurring in wildlife populations.

Using molecular methods, we examined diversity and prevalence of approximately 40 tick-borne pathogens in black-backed jackals (*Canis mesomelas*) caracals (*Caracal caracal*) and in the Central Karoo, as well as caracal population in Namaqualand and the Cape Peninsula of South Africa. We aimed to explore the extent of pathogen infection in wildlife species interacting with humans and their domestic animals. Among jackals, only 44% of the population were infected by one or more of the target species while caracals showed 100% prevalence of infection with at least one haemoparasite species. Pathogen diversity in caracals varied significantly across study sites but no overlap of pathogens was observed between sympatric jackals and caracals. Phylogenetic analysis revealed extensive pathogen diversity, and provided insight into the epizootiology of disease in these predators.

This work contributes to our knowledge of black-backed jackals pathogen diversity and represents the first detailed study of blood pathogens and disease in caracals. It provides a first step in understanding how predator pathogens vary in rural and urban landscapes, and proved critical baseline data in the Karoo region, which faces imminent land use change impacts.

Assessing diet, prey preference and niche overlap of sympatric mesocarnivores on farmland versus a nature reserve

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In this study, we compare the diet of black-backed jackals (*Canis mesomelas*) and caracals (*Caracal caracal*) living on either small-livestock farms or a nature reserve in the Karoo region of South Africa. We used these data to investigate the impacts of small livestock farming on predator diet including prey preference and niche overlap. A combined total of 670 scats were collected opportunistically between 2012 and 2015 from both sites. We calculated frequency of occurrence, percent mass and percent volume of each food item in the faeces and used biomass models to determine the amount of ingested food per diet category.

Mesopredator diet varied markedly between areas with sheep being the most consumed prey on farmland for both jackal (n=216) and caracal (n=102). Despite this, only jackal exhibited a preference for sheep, with caracal consuming fewer than predicted by relative abundance. Both species showed a strong preference for micromammals on farmland and in the reserve. Within the reserve, jackals fed predominantly on fruits/seeds (n=201) while caracals (n=80) fed primarily on micromammals. Jackals and caracals on farmland had a greater niche breadth than in the reserve and niche overlap was greatest between caracals and jackals in the reserve.

Together these results confirm previous findings that mesopredators have adapted to include domestic livestock in their diet despite having a clear preference for micromammals in natural habitat. These differences illustrate a shift to feeding between the two land-use types with these results highlighting the importance of rodents for the two mesopredators.

Urbanization drives genetic divergence in the isolated Cape Peninsula caracal (*Caracal caracal*) population

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As the urban-wildland interface expands, wildlife populations are increasingly isolated. Genetic effects include reduced effective population size, increased population substructure, decreased genetic variation, and increased vulnerability to extinction. We studied populations of caracals (*Caracal caracal*) that experience varied degrees of isolation in and around Cape Town. In Cape Town, caracals inhabit patchy open space. Yet the city itself may be a near-absolute barrier to movement between the isolated Cape Town population and nearby populations in large protected and agricultural areas. We genotyped 83 individuals from four populations sampled between 2014-2016 for variation at 15 microsatellites. We compared genetic variation and differentiation between the populations to assess the relative roles of geographic distance and urbanization as drivers of genetic change. We found that the Cape Town barrier has caused more genetic differentiation between populations than between populations separated by >20-fold distances spanning open, connected landscape. Further, a genetic bottleneck in the isolated urban population has caused decreased genetic variation on a short time scale (estimated ≤ 30 years). We detected two genetic migrants in the isolated population, but little evidence of their genetic contribution to the population. Some wildlife populations may be near-absolutely isolated beyond the point of no return in rapidly urbanizing areas. Other urban stressors can compound the effects of genetic isolation and increase the vulnerability of populations to local extinction. Our findings underscore the maintenance of functional habitat connectivity via the protection of wildlife corridors is essential to promoting biodiversity conservation over the long-term in rapidly urbanizing landscapes.

Evaluating sustainable international trade in wildlife using Non-detriment Finding Assessments: barriers and opportunities

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South Africa subscribes to sustainable use principles and thus trades internationally in a wide variety of animals. This trade is governed by the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES). In compliance with CITES and the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (No. 10 of 2004), Non-detriment Finding Assessments (NDF) are made for CITES Appendix I and II species to determine whether international trade is likely to be detrimental to the survival of the species in the wild. The NDF is a science-based risk assessment where the vulnerability of a species is considered in relation to how well harvest in the species and its trade is

managed. We analysed 10 NDFs done for internationally traded animals; six were negative (i.e. trade cannot be shown to be non-detrimental), three were positive (i.e. trade poses no detriment to wild populations) and one for which trade could not be shown to be either detrimental or non-detrimental to wild populations. All six of the negative NDF assessments arose as a result of concerns around the management of the species and its trade. Five of the six negative assessments were also driven by biology of the species making the species vulnerable to utilisation. However, for one assessment, the species biology was a high risk factor, yet the assessment was still positive because the management of the species is very effective. In light of the NDFs, we discuss the requirements for wildlife-based trade to become more sustainable in South Africa.

Hit and run! Reducing wildlife-vehicle-collisions in protected areas

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In 2014, the Endangered Wildlife Trust initiated an assessment of wildlife-vehicle collisions (WVC) within selected protected areas in South Africa. Of almost 700 questionnaire surveys conducted with visitors to protected areas, more than 95% of respondents to the questionnaire survey believed that speed was the main cause of WVCs. However, traffic monitoring devices deployed within the parks showed that 72% of park visitors (n=6,981) complied with park speed limits driving at or below the speed limit. We postulated that WVCs were likely to occur because drivers were either unaware of their surroundings or travelling too fast to avoid collisions. To investigate these factors, we placed two fake animals (a snake and an amphibian) on a 40 m section of road in two National Parks. We used traffic monitoring devices to record the speed at which the vehicles were being driven, and observational techniques to assess the position of the driver's head (looking straight ahead at the road or to the bush at the side) as well as the driver response to the fake animal (a 'hit' or a 'miss'). Of 201 vehicles, 67.7% of the drivers were not looking at the road, but rather scanning the bush for wildlife, and 49.6% of vehicles hit the fake animals. This suggests that WVCs in national parks happen primarily because of the expectation that animals are to be found in the habitat alongside the road, rather than on the road itself and that improving driver observation of the road, rather than the speed of the vehicle, is the key factor in preventing a WVC.

Poster Abstracts

Monday, 19 September 2016

(1)

Eskom/Endangered Wildlife Trust partnership 1996 – 2016: 20 years of working together to reduce impacts of the business on biodiversity and vice versa

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Eskom is responsible for providing electricity to meet the ever increasing needs of its end users. As a result, Eskom's electrical infrastructure is continuously being expanded upon to support annual load growth. Negative interactions between wildlife and electrical structure take on many forms including the electrocution of wildlife, birds colliding with powerlines and wildlife causing short circuits in the electricity supply through various activities on electricity structures. These interruptions to the power supply have dire consequences for large industries and residential areas. The challenge for Eskom is to find the balance between the electricity demands of the nation, the interests of industry, the residential electrification programme, and the effective use and conservation of natural, social and economic resources. In view of the complexity, scope and persistence of the problem of interactions between wildlife and powerlines, Eskom and the Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT) formalised their long-standing relationship by entering into a partnership in 1996 to address the problem in a systematic manner on a national basis and to establish an integrated management system to minimise these negative interactions. The Eskom/EWT strategic partnership evolved over the years to include other facets of the business including the power generation element. Activities include the assistance with the design of biodiversity action plans for all power-stations, and guidance on game management, alien plant management and the rehabilitation of ash dams. Additionally, EWT assists Eskom with the management of wildlife interactions across all Eskom infrastructure and through advising on all biodiversity related issues.

(2)

Seeking roadkill data through public awareness, partnerships and citizen science

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Roads are integral to the continued development and prosperity of South Africa's economy. However, roads also have the potential to destroy and degrade habitat, as well as fragment wildlife populations. Traffic, particularly when reckless driving is involved, can have a direct negative impact on wildlife, with many species at risk from wildlife-vehicle-collisions (WVCs), often resulting in an animal's death, or 'roadkill'.

The Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT) has improved our understanding of the impacts of road infrastructure on wildlife in South Africa over the last six years. We have been gathering WVC data from across the country by driving set routes and encouraging members of the public to submit data.

In January 2014 we launched a national public awareness campaign to report WVC sightings. As a result of these WVC reporting platforms, almost 10,000 roadkill data points have been collected with the assistance of over 150 volunteers from across the country. From these data, we have identified problem species and sites, and can develop and implement targeted measures to reduce wildlife-road-mortality.

Apart from public engagement, we are also establishing partnerships with relevant stakeholders, within the transport sector to provide measures to reduce the impacts of roads on wildlife as well as expand on current public awareness roadkill campaigns. Through these partnerships, we provide training workshops for data collection and species identification, and capacitate road patrol teams, as well as members of the public, to record and submit roadkill sightings from across the country.

(3)

Adaptive genetic variation within southern African mammal species

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Most population genetic research focus on neutral genetic variation as measured from (for example) mtDNA genes and microsatellite markers. However, adaptive genetic variation among/within animal species is an important aspect of genetic variation, which is readily overlooked during phylogeographic analyses. Analysis of neutral genetic variation can reveal population genetic structure and patterns of gene flow among populations. It does, however, not provide any information with regards to the adaptive significance of the observed genetic variation within/among populations. The study of adaptive genetic variation entails the use of nuclear gene regions directly involved in fitness and possibly subject to intense selective pressures. We are studying the adaptive variation of three southern African mammal species (*Rhabdomys pumilio*, *Chlorocebus pygerythrus* and *Antidorcas marsupialis*). The first two studies (*Rhabdomys pumilio* and *Chlorocebus pygerythrus*) aim to compare the adaptive genetic variation among populations distributed along a natural habitat gradient, using fitness linked genes. Both the *Rhabdomys pumilio* and *Chlorocebus pygerythrus* distribution ranges covers numerous habitat types. In theory, populations occurring in different habitat types will be exposed to different selective pressures. The third study aims to assess the genetic impact of intensive line breeding on fitness in antelope populations, using atypical springbok populations. An assessment of adaptive genetic variation among different colour morph populations using immune linked genes will provide insights into the effects of selective breeding on fitness in animal populations. Overall, results from these studies will help conservationists to better understand the influence of habitat differentiation and artificial selective breeding on animal populations.

(4)

***Ongediertes*: An ethnographic account of the political ecology of black-backed jackal management around the SKA core site**

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The Karoo, known primarily for its sheep farming as well as its vastness, remoteness and seeming emptiness, is currently facing changes. The erection of the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) radio telescope has drawn national and international attention to this semi-arid region as it promises to identify and understand some of the fundamental laws and structures of the universe. In order to ensure the ultimate functionality of the instruments, additional properties are being purchased around the SKA core site to act as a buffer zone. As the purchased land will be withdrawn from agricultural production and placed under conservation management, farmers on neighbouring privately-owned land have grown increasingly concerned since the expectation is that such a buffer zone will become a safe haven for numerous fauna, especially mesocarnivores such as black-backed jackals (*Canis*

mesomelas). By conducting semi-structured interviews and making use of participant observation, my research aims to unravel the political forces at work in human–black-backed jackal conflict on the boundary of the SKA core site. This will be done by analysing neighbouring farmers' attitudes toward the buffer zone; the social meanings attached to black-backed jackals; the power relations around knowledge production in relation to black-backed jackal management; how the management of black-backed jackals influences social capital; and if farmers' relationship with black-backed jackals symbolise their relationship with the SKA, or vice versa. Consequently, my study will highlight the human dimensions of human–wildlife conflict, along with the importance of collaborative working relationships between various stakeholders involved in wildlife management.

(5)

The dietary consequences of being an urban caracal: insight from classic and new methods

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With the rapid spread of urban development comes increasing exposure of wildlife to the novel challenges of cities. Human activities concentrate nutrients, often resulting in the growth of synanthropic animal populations. At the urban-wildland edge these enriched environments support higher densities of certain wildlife species and, in doing so, may intensify human-wildlife conflict. To implement effective management in these situations it is vital to understand the ecology of wildlife at the urban fringe. We investigated the diet of an apex predator, the caracal (*Caracal caracal*), at the urban-wildland interface in Cape Town, South Africa. Using GPS collar data, collected as part of a larger study on the ecology of caracal in the city, we ground truthed data clusters across the Cape Peninsula to locate prey remains, scats for hair and bone analysis, and resting beds. Our preliminary results reveal that these urban wild cats spend most of their foraging time within 100 m of the urban edge and have a diverse diet that includes wild, synanthropic and domestic species. These data suggest that while the urban fringe supports higher resource abundance on which caracals capitalize, increased prey availability may also raise the risk of mortality due to pesticide exposure, vehicle collision and retaliatory killing. Management agencies are challenged to develop and implement biodiversity policy that serves both households and the rich wildlife of Cape Town, centred as it is on a Natural World Heritage Site. We discuss a number of options that can impact positively on this urban predator.

Tuesday, 20 September 2016

(6)

Deriving a practical biodiversity value score for Protected Areas in Limpopo

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The Limpopo Department of Economic Development, Environment & Tourism (LEDET) manages a Protected Area Network consisting of a suite of provincial nature reserves. The Biodiversity Management directorate was requested to evaluate these reserves in terms of their importance to biodiversity. The intention is to use this assessment, in conjunction with similar economic and tourism assessments, as a strategic tool to guide management of the protected area network. The tool would be used to guide disposal of protected areas that were not contributing to biodiversity targets, and to prioritise actions in those of high biodiversity value.

It was decided to adopt a categorical scoring model similar to that used in IUCN assessments in preference to an aggregated numerical score. In the former option, hierarchical importance thresholds can be triggered by any of a number of criteria – this prevents areas from being ‘devalued’ by poor data availability. Another advantage is that a categorical importance rating cannot simply be absorbed into a composite importance score with tourism, economic or any other indices, ensuring that biodiversity value is not overlooked in strategic decision-making.

The tool was developed in Microsoft Excel using Noss’ (1990) biological complexity hierarchy as a point of departure. Twelve criteria were evaluated, ranging from genetic to landscape levels. Only protected areas where spatial data were available were evaluated. Of the protected areas evaluated, all had biodiversity importance, ranging from ‘Moderate Importance’ (n=6), through ‘High Importance’ (n=1) and ‘Very High Importance’ (n=26) to ‘Critical Importance’ (n=24).

(7)

Big trees versus big elephants: Is there room for both?

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Although no evidence exist of a linear relationship between elephant density and the impact they have on the vegetation in their environment, it is generally accepted that in fenced reserves, high elephant densities lead to bigger impact on large trees. Madikwe Game Reserve in the North West Province has the highest density of elephants in South Africa and was chosen as a study site to test this hypothesis. Elephant utilisation was assessed on different tree height classes to quantify the impact on large trees (defined as 5 m and taller). 1543 trees were measured and elephant utilisation recorded across 23 transects (100 m in length and 20 m wide). Preliminary results indicate that elephant utilisation overall is higher in larger trees, having a higher frequency of debarking, breaking of the main trunk, uprooting and mortality. The intensity of large tree utilisation is seen to be proportional to abundance across vegetation types, with the type of utilisation being dependent on tree species. Vegetation structure and large tree mortality was also influenced by other factors, including fire. Elephant utilisation can thus not be regarded as the only influence on vegetation structure. Data collection is still to be completed before meaningful conclusions can be drawn as not all vegetation types have been sampled yet. Management should consider altering elephant distribution and movement patterns through manipulation of nutrient resources such as water points to avoid over utilisation of highly utilised areas and to encourage utilisation in areas of bush encroachment.

(8)

Using DNA from Giraffe (*Giraffa camelopardalis*) fecal samples to determine diversity within populations

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Giraffe are found on many reserves and private properties in Central South Africa, but individual population sizes are in many cases quite small. This is due to lack of suitable habitat and/or the fact that only a few individuals of the species are often kept to increase species diversity. Small population size and lack of gene flow with the wider national giraffe population can result in local loss of genetic diversity. The negative effects of such loss are well-known, and include both short term effects relating to loss of genetic diversity and possible genetic drift; and loss of adaptability in the longer term. Furthermore, no data is available on the genetic structure of giraffe in Central South Africa, and the

possible effect of translocations on natural patterns of diversity.

In this study, we are using DNA isolated from fecal samples to determine levels of genetic diversity within and between giraffe populations. Initial results show that amplification of the Cytochrome B (CytB) gene region in the mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) from fecal samples yields good results, with a useable sequence length of ~500 base-pairs, although with low variability. Continuing research is aimed at (i) comparing genetic characteristics of small and control populations; (ii) comparing populations from Central South Africa to information available for other populations from the GenBank database; and (iii) amplifying additional gene regions with potentially higher levels of polymorphism.

(9)

Mammal diversity and density in transformed and natural landscapes of a conservation corridor adjacent to the Garden Route National Park, Western Cape Province

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Camera traps are used as a research tool for a variety of reasons. Here we use them to determine the density and diversity of medium sized mammals that use the corridor linking Garden Route National Park with Goukamma Nature Reserve. This enables a comparison between mammals utilizing natural land use types and land under anthropogenic influence. Between three and four camera traps were placed in four different land use types, two natural and two under anthropogenic influence. They were spaced about 300 meters apart along trails, game paths or roads and were checked and moved to a different location, but same land use types within the corridor every three weeks. It was found that species density and diversity differed significantly between land use types, which is most likely due to anthropogenic influences as well as habitat requirements (food, shelter, breeding cover, distance from water) of the relevant species.

(10)

Impala spatial and temporal habitat utilization and movement patterns in Loskop Mountain Bushveld and Loskop Thornveld

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Monitoring Impala seasonal habitat utilisation and movement patterns provides wildlife managers with valuable information for managing the species and their habitats. Using GPS satellite collars to record Impala movements with high temporal frequency provides information on their behaviour and how they interact with their environment. We used fixed kernel density estimation to calculate seasonal home range size and core utilisation areas. Seasonal daily distances travelled were determined and compared. The influence of rainfall, temperature and photoperiod on ranging behaviour was modelled to determine which variables influence seasonal ranging patterns the most. Findings indicate that in Loskop Mountain Bushveld and Loskop Thornveld, Impala show marked seasonal variation in the way they utilise their home ranges. Home range size varied from 970ha in the dry season to 391ha in the wet season. Core area utilisation varied from 21% in the dry season to 39% in the wet season. Day ranges varied seasonally with longer distances travelled during the dry season ($\bar{x} = 1.09\text{km}$) when resources are scarce, compared to the wet season ($\bar{x} = 0.93\text{km}$) when resources are abundant. Seasonal variation in day ranges indicates that Impala adapt their movement patterns to resource availability, which in turn is driven by environmental conditions. Photoperiod has the biggest impact on

daily distances travelled in the dry season while temperature has the most important affect in the wet season. Seasonal differences in habitat utilisation and movement patterns are indicative of the mixed feeding status attributed to Impala, highlighting the relatively opportunistic and unspecialised manner in which they feed.

(11)

Using non-invasive genetic sampling to assess population size and genetic viability of isolated black rhino populations

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The black rhinoceros (*Diceros bicornis*) has suffered enormous reductions in range and population size during the 20th century, with numbers decreasing to just a few thousand animals remaining in the wild. With the dramatic increase in poaching in recent years, effective monitoring and management plans are essential to ensure long-term viability of the species. Most of these rhino occur in small, isolated populations that are susceptible to founder effects, inbreeding depression and reduced genetic viability and survival. Traditional monitoring techniques can be difficult in certain vegetation biomes when assessing elusive species, and cannot provide fine-scale population level information. Non-invasive genetic sampling reduces the disturbance to animals/populations, eliminates the need for anaesthesia and handling, and provides individual identification and population data. Thus we are developing a non-invasive monitoring protocol using faecal DNA sampling to estimate population parameters and genetic viability in black rhino. Fresh faecal samples were collected along roads, trails and at water points within a SANParks reserve and optimised for storage and DNA extraction. Extracted DNA was quantified and tested for quality by amplifying established black rhino microsatellite markers. The number of individual animals within the full faecal sample set was determined. Fluorescent genotyping will be performed at 10 black rhino microsatellite loci on all samples of sufficient quality. Genetic diversity, inbreeding statistics and effective population size will be calculated for the population. Breeding success of individuals will be determined in order to inform future metapopulation management and translocation decisions.

(12)

Carnivore intra-guild competition at Selati Game Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa

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Terrestrial ecosystems generally contain multiple carnivore species which not only compete for shared resources but also pose a threat to one another. Carnivore intra-guild competition can be particularly intense as carnivores are both morphologically and behaviourally adapted for killing. Although the only intact guild of large carnivores can be found in Africa, our understanding of the extent of intra-guild competition is heavily biased towards canids in the northern hemisphere. Previous research has focused on the role of direct killing and interactions between pairs of carnivore species, completely overlooking the interactions occurring among subordinate carnivores. A better understanding of the complex interactions of multiple-carnivore communities is therefore needed. South Africa has very few free-ranging large carnivores, as most reserves are completely bound by electrified, predator-proof

fencing. Many of the reserves are also small (<400km²), which could increase the likelihood of competition among carnivores, as artificially high population densities are created due to the clumping of competing carnivores. The ways in which multiple carnivore species utilize and partition space and resources in small, enclosed reserves is currently poorly understood. An intensive camera trap survey, diet analyses and road-strip censuses, along with data collected from collared large carnivores, will be used to determine the interactions of carnivores found on a small, enclosed reserve in South Africa. Understanding how multiple carnivores utilize available resources within small, enclosed systems is vital for their conservation, as it provides insight into the ecological needs of species and can aid the development of management plans for enclosed reserves.

(13)

Amphibians and vegetation as indicators of conservation value of wetlands in an anthropogenically impacted landscape

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The environmental condition of earth is of global concern, with the anthropogenic effects of man impacting various functions of the ecosystem through land modification and fragmentation. Wetlands are crucial in maintaining the water purity of an area, providing protection against floods, and constituting vital habitat for a diverse suite of species. This study aimed to characterise the conservation value of wetlands in three land use types namely: Fynbos, plantations, and modified recreational land. Vegetation and amphibians were sampled, in both breeding and non-breeding season. Distance sampling was used to measure amphibian population density. Species seen during sampling, adhoc sighting and call recording were used to determine species diversity. Data for both vegetation and amphibians were scored and summed to give the wetland a total conservation score, this final score allows for a comparison of conservation value between wetlands in different land use types. We found significant differences in conservation scores between land use types which seemed to be attributed to the availability of water and human impact.

(14)

Herpetological biodiversity in areas adjacent to the Wilderness Section of the Garden Route National Park, Western Cape, South Africa

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A combination of various anthropogenic driven changes (i.e. habitat destruction, climate change, pollution, and alien species introduction) is leading to the decline in amphibian and reptile (i.e. herpetofauna) populations on a global scale. Knowledge of the effect of various anthropogenic driven changes have on herpetofauna in South Africa is lacking. This research focused on unravelling the herpetological biodiversity patterns in an anthropogenically changed landscape in and around the Garden Route National Park, Western Cape, South Africa. The main objective was to accumulate an inventory of herpetological biodiversity. We used pitfall traps and funnel traps along Y-shape drift fence arrays as well as visual encounter surveys diurnally. A conservation score as well as the trap success rate was calculated for each sample site. There was a notable difference between species diversity and trap success between the different sample areas which could partially be attributed to human disturbance.

SAHGCA Sponsored Session: “Bridging the divide” - The “currency” of the wildlife economy?

National Parks for Society – Rationale, challenges and opportunities

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Not only do national parks serve as important refuges for biological species and systems, but globally, parks are perceived as critical components of human life support systems. In this context, parks are expected to do more than ever before. South African National Parks (SANParks) face several challenges in achieving this dual purpose, driven in part by the complex history of both parks and South Africa as a whole. Histories of forced removals and restricted access and a lack of understanding of varying value systems between stakeholders, has contributed to a lack of conservation constituency in some cases especially where conservation related costs occur. Furthermore, large, primarily low-income human populations adjacent to some parks (e.g. Kruger) have given rise to unrealistic expectations regarding the potential of parks to contribute to sustainable development. Economically, SANParks was heavily subsidised by the South African Government for their intrinsic value but recent subsidy decreases have resulted in a need for internal revenue generation.

This conflicting need to make more money while sharing benefits more fairly, in the context of remaining ecologically intact, economically viable and socially acceptable has called for innovative ways of thinking about benefit production, management, distribution and accrual in SANParks. Based on a combination of literature reviews and individual and group discussions, a framework for collectively auditing benefits has been developed, highlighting four main benefit categories: employment and business opportunities, capacity building and awareness, infrastructure support and ecosystem services. Together with processes of managing relationships and restoring rights as well as understanding the links between benefit distribution, human well-being and conservation constituency, the framework has contributed to a deeper understanding of the drivers of more effective benefit sharing from protected areas.

The Currency of Farmed Wildlife in southern Africa: A master quest of environmental health, bio-economic growth and species enhancement

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The species enhancement of the Bontebok *Damaliscus pygargus* came into question with the US Fisheries & Wildlife Services from an attack by the US Humane Society in October 2015. A comprehensive report that enlightens the origin, development and reasons for the genetic bottleneck of the sub-species was compiled which acts as a valued argument which defines and supports the positive realm of farmed wildlife. An assessment of governmental attempts of protection *verses* the translocation of Bontebok out of its past natural distribution range in the Western Cape to alternative more suitable habitat on private farmed land in the Eastern Cape and the Free State, and a difference in number of 1,200 *versus* 8,000 bontebok with regards to farmed wildlife are discussed. Substantiated explanation of genetic heterozygosity, linked to historic palaeontology of the southern African coast line and the climate

conditions and consequent different vegetation as now indicated from dental radio-isotope measurements from fossils, support the genetic quiz of isolation management of sub-populations/farms against cross translocations. The context of inbreeding *verses* genetic diversity and natural species fitness are being discussed. The role of custodian species breeder's societies for farmed wildlife in terms of DEA and DAFF regulations and with regard to species enhancement and research needs are discussed with a twist. Strategic statistics of farmed wildlife are presented and discussed against legal implications and terms of different National Acts of legislation including NEMBA and the Animal Improvement Act (Act 62 of 1998).

The conservation costs of game ranching

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The devolution of user rights of wildlife in southern Africa has led to a widespread land-use shift from livestock farming to game ranching. The economic advantages of game ranching over livestock farming are significant, but so too are the risks associated with breeding financially valuable game where free-ranging wildlife pose a credible threat. Here, we assessed whether the conservation potential of game ranching, and a decentralized approach to conservation more generally, may be undermined by an increase in human-wildlife conflict. We demonstrate that game rancher tolerance towards free-ranging wildlife has significantly decreased as the game ranching industry has evolved. Our findings reveal a conflict of interest between wealth and wildlife conservation resulting from local decision-making in the absence of adequate centralized governance and evidence-based best practice. As a fundamental pillar of devolution-based natural resource management, game ranching proves an important mechanism for economic growth, albeit at a significant cost to conservation.

The environmental costs of intensive game breeding in South Africa: Mapping the rate of change in game fences at two sites in Limpopo Province from 2006-2015

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The rapid expansion of intensive wildlife breeding in the South Africa over the past decade has raised concerns regarding the environmental impacts of this industry. As a first step towards understanding the environmental costs of this industry we estimate the extent and growth of this industry by mapping at the extent and rate of change in new fencing in the landscape at two sites (208 properties, 195 512 ha). This was done in the upper Limpopo Valley near Thabazimbi from satellite imagery at three time periods: 2006, 2010 and 2015. Between 2006 and 2015: (1) the total length of internal fencing across both study sites increases by 22% or 814 km from 3702 km to 4517 km; (2) The average annual change in length of new fence increases by 64% in the second period from 69 km/year (2006-2010) to 108 km/year (2010-2015); (3) The number of intensive breeding properties increases from 8 properties (4% of total) in 2006 to 17 (8%) in 2010, and reaching 51 (25% of total) in 2015; (4) There is an overall reduction in camp size and increase in the total number of camps. Median camp size decreases by 106% from 35.5 ha in 2006 to 17.2 ha in 2015, and the total number of camps increases by 46% from

3129 in 2006 to 4582 in 2015; and, (5) The area occupied by very small camps (i.e. less than 10 ha in size) increases between 2006 and 2015 by 87% from 3619 ha to 6769 ha. The conversion from extensive to intensive farming is associated with a reduction in camp size and a proliferation of new fences in the landscape. Also, intensive wildlife breeding is currently expanding rapidly and exponentially in this landscape.

Desperation to Opportunity: Protected areas unlocking rural wildlife economies?

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State conservation agencies are experiencing significant financial constraints and the land under their protection is seen by many to be unproductive, and an economic burden not contributing to South Africa's socio-economic challenges. The consequence of this perception renders protected areas at risk from continued reduction in conservation funding with a greater political emphasis being placed on protected areas (or at least conservation agencies) being self-funded. Similarly, neighbouring rural communities often see little value in protected areas and a view them as a source of conflict. Since time immemorial, conservation agencies have attempted to justify the existence of protected areas on ethical and legal grounds, and more recently by way of ecosystem services, and adaptation to and mitigation of climate change. While these arguments are valid, the majority of South Africa's protected areas remain vulnerable islands within an economically depressed and politically challenging landscape. To meet this challenge, without the state abdicating on its fiduciary trust duties, the philosophical approach to protected areas needs to be overhauled or replaced with a new landscape-economy paradigm.

Following from a situational analysis of a Zululand case study, this paper discusses how the traditional insular and purist conservation approaches to protected area management are significant hurdles to securing, in the long term, the protected area's viability and sustainability. It further demonstrates how, through innovative approaches and partnerships, protected areas can anchor and unlock rural economic growth in marginalised communities whilst simultaneously improving conservation performance and transformation of the wildlife economy.

Do we manage for growth in numbers or sustainable contribution?

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The wildlife industry makes a huge contribution to the provision of ecological goods and services, such as clean air, water, food and materials, valued at R73 billion or 3% of the national Gross Domestic Product, in South Africa. The wildlife economy further generated an estimated R9.1 billion for the economy in 2013, while making substantial contributions to conservation. Extensive wildlife systems further supports the eco-tourism industry that has been identified as a key sector for economic growth in South Africa. Within the wildlife ranching sector of the industry, the two most significant growth periods coincided with shifts from extensive game farming to intensive and selective breeding of game for commercial purposes. In this paper, two case studies will be discussed briefly, highlighting how both management and regulatory practices impact on the current and future potential of this sector to contribute to ecosystem services, the economy and national conservation targets. Species level and cumulative impacts at a landscape and industry level will be highlighted. The conundrum facing wildlife managers and regulators is how to assess and mitigate negative impacts and incorporate this into strategies to grow a responsible wildlife industry that will be socially, economically and environmentally responsible and sustainable.

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Southern African Wildlife Management Association

SAWMA The Southern African Wildlife Management Association is an independent, voluntary professional body, founded in 1970. The Association is involved with the science and management of wildlife and other renewable natural resources. SAWMA has a multi-disciplinary base and includes disciplines such as wildlife research, ecology, conservation science and animal science. SAWMA acts as a forum for interaction between scientists, researchers, wildlife managers, students, conservationists, environmentalists, game producers and game farm owners. This is achieved through regular newsletters (SAWMA Matters), a scientific journal (African Journal of Wildlife Research) and the annual symposium.

Vision:

SAWMA is dedicated to the conservation and wise management of the wildlife resources of southern Africa.

Primary Objectives:

- To provide a forum for communication between wildlife managers in southern Africa;
- To encourage research and publish a scientific journal devoted to results of such research;
- To provide a reference and liaison service to members through a regular newsletter;
- To assist in the co-ordination of wildlife research in southern Africa;
- To provide professional and technical expertise.

Online membership registration can be done at the following link:
http://www.sawma.co.za/wild_member.php

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Website: www.sawma.co.za